

EXCELERATE Deliverable D1.1

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Table of content

1. Executive Summary	2
2. Project objectives	3
3. Delivery and schedule.....	3
4. Adjustments made.....	3
5. Background information	3
Annex 1: Registry release with comprehensive coverage of ELIXIR Node resources, including resource data format curation and analysis	7

1. Executive Summary

Life sciences are yielding huge datasets that underpin scientific discoveries fundamental to improvement in human health, agriculture and the environment. In support of these discoveries, a plethora of databases and tools are deployed, in technically complex and diverse implementations, across a spectrum of scientific disciplines. The corpus of documentation of these resources is fragmented across the Web, with much redundancy, and has lacked a common standard of information. The outcome is that scientists must often struggle to discover and use the best resources for the task at hand.

The objective of EXCELERATE Deliverable 1.1 is the development of a discovery portal (bio.tools) built upon a federated curation of a wide range of key software resources for bioinformatics worldwide. The core aim is to provide a practical portal that will help scientists not only find, understand, compare, and select resources (“discovery”), but also use and connect them in workflows (“interoperability”). Underpinning the portal is a registry of software information; the cornerstone of the WP.

Four reports directly concerning the registry are due throughout the duration of the EXCELERATE project, one per project year:

- prototyping of portal software and registry data model, addition of seed content
- consolidation of software features and content to a stable model
- expansion of registry content towards comprehensive coverage, with new registry features
- integration with other software systems, registry applications and portal impact evaluation

This report describes the initial prototyping of the portal building upon an early prototype launched in 2015, including development of the community-driven curation effort that is working towards a comprehensive and consistent registry of information - recently published in *Nucleic Acids Research*. To ensure the needs of all stakeholders - including content providers and end-users - were satisfied, an agile, user-centered development process was adopted from the outset: implementation priorities have been set by and delivered with the help of the community.

This deliverable report describes work done with ELIXIR/EXCELERATE resources including:

- process and outcomes of build-up of the community contributing to the portal
- model for describing software, which uses the EDAM ontology and miscellaneous controlled vocabularies to describe software using a set of unique defined terms
- initial registry content, formatted according to the model (above)
- software including a client-side application (query interface, registration interface), and a server-side application (back-end database, administrator tooling, API)

Detailed information on technical components is included. All aspects of the project are interdependent and work is ongoing in all areas, in light of anticipated content growth, new registry features, integration scenarios and applications. The report describes progress made thus far and includes a summary of anticipated developments in the funding period.

2. Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

No.	Objective	Yes	No
1	Deliver a discovery portal built upon a federated curation of a wide range of key resources for bioinformatics resources world-wide	x	
2	Service monitoring, resource integration, interoperability aspects, and community centred benchmarking efforts		x
3	Deliver impact for end-users across academia, health organizations, and industry		x

3. Delivery and schedule

The delivery is delayed: Yes No

4. Adjustments made

No adjustments were made.

5. Background information

Background information on this WP as originally indicated in the description of action (DoA) is included here for reference.

Work package number	1	Start date or starting event:	month 1
Work package title	Tools Interoperability and Service Registry		
Lead	Søren Brunak (DK) and Alfonso Valencia (ES)		
Participant number and person months per participant			
1 - EMBL (12 PM), 2 - UOXF (6 PM), 5 - UTARTU (43 PM), 7 - CNIO (2 PM), 8 - CRG (11 PM), 10 - IRB (8 PM), 17 - INESC-ID (4 PM), 21 - UiB (18 PM), 25 - SIB (9.5 PM), 26 - CNRS (9 PM), 29 - IP (12 PM), 35 - MU (18.2 PM), 38 - DTU (76 PM)			

Objectives

- Deliver a discovery portal built upon a federated curation of a wide range of key resources for bioinformatics resources world-wide
- Service monitoring, resource integration, interoperability aspects, and community centred benchmarking efforts
- Deliver impact for end-users across academia, health organizations, and industry

Description of work and role of partners

Based on its first release in January 2015, WP1 will further develop the ELIXIR registry mechanism, interfaces and content upkeep strategy. The WP contains plans for the development and extension of its functionality and scope (Tasks 1.1, 1.2 and 1.5). The federated curation of the registry will ensure comprehensive content and high quality annotations, both of which are essential for the sustainable impact of the registry in the community. Scientific and technical consistency and utility will be achieved by using the EDAM controlled vocabulary. Exposing the results of efforts addressing tool benchmarking and monitoring of the resources listed in the registry will provide the end-user with a robust, scientifically relevant measure of tool quality and performance. Furthermore, the work on workbench integration and interoperability will lower the cost to developers of integrating their resources in key workflow environments, and assist the users with establishing and updating their day-to-day workflows. Finally, WP1 contains plans for comprehensive, registry related user support, which will ensure impact for users, and a dynamic management element, including marketing and community development to build the federated organization behind the registry. The user-centric approach will thus stand as the guiding principle for the entire portal and guard its relevance to the community.

Task 1.1: Federated Registry Curation (96 PM)

This task will deliver essential scientific and technical coverage in the registry and the vocabulary (EDAM) that underpins registry consistency and utility. A major community curation effort is required, including vocabulary development, resource annotation and registration. To ensure that the curation is high quality and sustainable, it must be federated across registry stakeholders, hence a major priority is building and supporting the community of federated curators. In tandem, the curation will be accompanied by focused software and other technical developments, that automate, validate and embed the curation process in relevant software systems; the essential underpinning of sustainability.

The registry has two primary purposes; to help discover tools and services and use them. Discovery means to find, understand, compare and select. It is a prerequisite to (inter)operability, which demands a precise understanding of software dependencies. Our approach is based on the acceptance that software interoperability will, for the foreseeable future, be implemented primarily by developers rather than intelligent software agents. We will therefore, once a comprehensive set of ELIXIR Node resources are described in basic detail, extend the curation of the registry to annotate, using EDAM Format URIs (unified resource identifiers), the data formats that are supported by tools and data services. From this, we will analyse the format-usage landscape to provide a basis for targeted software developments to improve interoperability of registered resources. We foresee these developments, which might include conversion of tools to use common formats, and development of format- converter software where needed, to be facilitated via the Matchmaking Service mechanism (D1.5).

The registry scope will be: 1. Comprehensive coverage of ELIXIR Node resources, including tools, data services (APIs) and host databases, prioritising ELIXIR-badged services and new resources from the Use Cases. 2. Coverage of other biomedical science Research Infrastructures (RIs), and key resources beyond ELIXIR (European and non-European). A task force will be comprised of ontology developers, curators, scientific domain experts and relevant technical experts. It will run Curation and Usability hackathons with the recurrent theme of curation: resource annotation and registration, with necessary EDAM development. To facilitate networking and community build-up, two types of social event will be combined with the hackathons: 1. Knowledge Exchange Workshops, including representatives of relevant infrastructures, institutes and projects, on themes related to the registry suggested by the community. 2. Cross-domain Strategy Workshops to gather technical officers from ELIXIR Nodes, RIs, key resources, and other key initiatives, to discuss and develop common approaches for registry curation across RIs internationally.

EDAM provides the registry with a consistent vocabulary for topics (general scientific and technical disciplines), operations (tool functions), types of data, and specific data formats and data identifiers. Task 1.1 will work with the existing EDAM community, develop its open governance and contribution mechanisms and deliver essential utilities to ensure that maintenance, validation and community development is sustainable in the long term. We will assess and validate coverage by correlating EDAM concepts to terms used for curation, which will then inform and drive necessary additions and desirable clean-ups (removal of concepts). We will develop focused essential utilities for EDAM maintenance including automation of the release process, basic validation of content, reporting of changes between versions, deployment to ontology browsers such as BioPortal and OLS, technical integration of EDAM with applications including the registry and others, mapping of provider-supplied terms and phrases to EDAM, and revise annotation upon new EDAM releases.

To underpin the sustainability of the federated curation, this task will deliver focused software and other technical developments that will automate the registration and update of provider-supplied information, leveraging their own local software infrastructure where possible. We will work with providers to support them in doing this, and, where possible, adapt technically the local solutions to make them more broadly applicable to others. Further, in order to facilitate coverage, all relevant resource providers will be given smooth and convenient access to resource registration. This will be achieved by a combination of simple-to-obtain local login accounts and opening for using eduGAIN authentication to register resources.

Finally, this task will ensure that registered resource are citable, discoverable by the major search engines, and are placed in scientific context. It will also include technical mark-up to support “Semantic Web” applications, e.g. Schema.org-compatible microdata or RDFa to support Google “rich snippets” and other structured search results in the major browsers. Hence, the registry will promote the registered resources and deliver impact for developers and institutes by making resources rank higher in search results and hence more findable.

Task 1.1 partners: DK, NO, FR, CH, CZ, EMBL-EBI, PT

Task 1.2: Benchmarking and Monitoring (15PM)

This task will support the monitoring and community benchmarking of analytical tools, in a systematic and sustainable way e.g. based on the efforts in WP2. Firstly, it will review the existing service quality and performance metrics and assess their usefulness in the context of a registry. This may require development of a light-weight controlled

vocabulary capturing the concepts distilled from the preparatory activities above and those of WP2.

Task 1.2 partners: DK, ES, CZ, CH

Task 1.3: Workbench integration and interoperability (36PM)

There is general trend towards the use of workflows as a preferred environment for the convenient use of tools and data access, especially when resources must be used in combination with one another. This task will boost convenience and resource interoperability by implementing a Workbench Integration Enabler service that will develop the vision “register your software once - get it supported everywhere”. Technically, this service will translate the description of any tool or service that is registered in the Tools and Data Services Registry into the metadata format required by the existing major workbenches, including Mobyle, Galaxy and Taverna. Furthermore, we will develop a new, lightweight Service Launchpad for running tools and services which have programmatic access and which can be invoked using information available in the registry.

To develop the Enabler Service, we will align the registry software description model and the schemas used by the workbench systems or required by the Launchpad, and subsequently revise the model and schemas to facilitate the metadata transfer. Furthermore, to prove the principle, new high priority tools and services, including those developed in the Use Cases.

Task 1.3 partners: DK, EE, FR, CH, PT

Task 1.4: User support and derived registry development (36.7PM)

This task will provide direct and indirect user support to deliver impact for ELIXIR end-users. Direct support will be achieved primarily by leveraging the existing and highly popular user bioinformatics forums (BioStars, BioPlanet etc.). A User-support specialist will patrol such forums and respond to questions in one of four ways: 1) Where resources answering to the Users needs exist in the registry, a link to them in the registry will be provided via our API. 2) Where resources exist in the registry, but the registry API cannot be used to answer the question directly, they will request new features of the API and in so doing drive development of the Query Interface. 3) Where an appropriate resource exists but has not been registered, they will request the appropriate registry curator add it to the registry. 4) Where a registered resource exists that is close, but not quite what is required, they will forward feature requests to the appropriate developers, possibly via the Matchmaking Service (D1.5).

Indirect user support will be achieved primarily by ensuring the registry interfaces are highly usable and match very closely the needs of the user. To achieve this, we will run user experience sessions during the Curation and Usability h community. Scientific and technical consistency and utility will be achieved by using the EDAM controlled vocabulary. Exposing the results of efforts addressing tool benchmarking and monitoring of the resources listed in the registry will provide the end-user with a robust, scientifically relevant measure of tool quality and performance. Furthermore, the hackathons (see Task 1.1) in order to evaluate usability. We will develop comprehensive Good Practice Guidelines for the curation of the registry in all aspects, but in particular the annotation of common types of resources using EDAM. We will also participate in the development of an ELIXIR Experts Registry where users can discover relevant expertise within the ELIXIR network, and an ELIXIR User Helpdesk to answer general questions concerning use of the registry, forwarding specialised scientific and technical enquiries to relevant

experts.

Task 1.4 partners: DK, CH

Task 1.5: Management, marketing and community build-up (46PM)

This task will build the federated organisation primarily by identifying and facilitating key collaborations between registry stakeholders. This will be achieved by organising 'Resource Synergy Meetings', where we will identify and encourage targeted software developments, e.g. to coordinate curation and data sharing. We will also promote resource integration and usability, e.g. by cross-linking resources and through API harmonization. As a prerequisite to these Synergy Meetings, a Resource Metadata Catalogue, listing all relevant resources, their scientific and technical scope, and information fields (schema), will be compiled and used to compare providers and identify redundancies. We will also use these meeting to cross-link the Tools & Data Services Registry with other key ELIXIR registries, for example the Training Materials Registry, the ELIXIR Events Registry, and the Experts Registry.

This task will also develop an oversight and management strategy and leverage partners within and beyond the ELIXIR organisation to implement strategy. To drive delivery, it will identify and encourage collaboration, monitor actions, identify delays, and intervene where necessary. It will raise community awareness and therefore impact by contributing to a forceful marketing campaign via all appropriate marketing channels, including popular social media. It will provide support to funders, publishers and others at the EU and national level, that policy is aligned with the aims of the registry organisation.

Task 1.5 partners: DK

Annex 1: Registry release with comprehensive coverage of ELIXIR Node resources, including resource data format curation and analysis

Registry release with comprehensive coverage of ELIXIR Node resources, including resource data format curation and analysis

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Table of contents

1. Executive Summary	3
2. Technical overview	4
3. Community build-up process	5
3.1. Scope of the registry	7
3.2. Distributed community curation	8
4. Software description model	9
4.1. Software attributes	10
4.2. Model of tool function	11
4.3. EDAM ontology	12
4.4. Controlled vocabularies	13
5. Portal content	14
5.1. Content summary	14
5.2. Content annotation	15
6. Portal software	15
6.1. Registration interface	16
6.2. Query interface	17
6.2.1. Search bar	17
6.2.2. Summary view	18
6.2.3. Grid view	19
6.2.4. Tool Cards	19
6.3. Back-end architecture	20
6.3.1. Back-end database	20
6.3.2. Tool IDs and persistent URLs	20
6.3.3. Account management	21
6.3.4. Administrator tooling	22
6.3.5. API	22
7. Future Work	23
Appendix A: Founding principles	26
Appendix B: Community details	28
Appendix C: Candidate stable schema	32
Appendix D: Software architecture	45

Tables and Figures

Table 1 Tool types.....	7
Table 2 Mandatory attributes.....	10
Table 3 Attribute groups.....	11
Table 4 Planned registry feature and content development.....	23
Figure 1 <i>Registry architecture</i>	4
Figure 2 Tool function in biotoolsXSD.....	12
Figure 3 Model of EDAM concept.....	12
Figure 4 EDAM ontology.....	13
Figure 5 Registry content.....	15
Figure 6 Registry contributors.....	15
Figure 7 Registration interface.....	16
Figure 8 EDAM annotation widget.....	17
Figure 9 bio.tools search bar.....	17
Figure 10 bio.tools search bar (drill-down).....	18
Figure 11 Query interface (summary view).....	19
Figure 12 Query interface (grid view).....	19
Figure 13 Tool cards.....	20
Figure 14 User authentication.....	21
Figure 15 User profile page.....	21
Figure 16 Admin panel.....	22
Figure 17 Admin panel (editing).....	22
Figure 18 Client-side application architecture.....	45
Figure 19 Client-side application components.....	46
Figure 20 Server-side application architecture.....	48
Figure 21 Server-side application components.....	49
Figure 22 Server architecture.....	52

1. Executive Summary

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The objective of EXCELERATE Deliverable 1.1 is the development of a discovery portal (bio.tools¹) built upon a federated curation of a wide range of key software resources for bioinformatics worldwide. The core aim is to provide a practical portal that will help scientists not only find, understand, compare, and select resources (“discovery”), but also use and connect them in workflows (“interoperability”). Underpinning the portal is a registry of software information; the cornerstone of the WP.

Four reports directly concerning the registry are due (D1.1 - D1.4). Their primary focus is:

- **prototyping** of portal software and registry data model, addition of seed content (project month 12)
- **consolidation** of software features and content to a stable model (project month 24)
- **expansion** of registry content towards comprehensive coverage, with new registry features (project month 36)
- **integration** with other software systems, registry applications and portal impact evaluation (project month 48)

This report describes the initial prototyping of the portal building upon an early prototype launched in 2015, including development of the community-driven curation effort that is working towards a comprehensive and consistent registry of information - recently published in Nucleic Acids Research². To ensure the needs of all stakeholders - including content providers and end-users - were satisfied, an agile, user-centered development process was adopted from the outset: implementation priorities have been set by and delivered with the help of the community.

This deliverable report describes work done with ELIXIR/EXCELERATE resources including:

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- software including a client-side application (query interface, registration interface), and a server-side application (back-end database, administrator tooling, API)

Detailed information on technical components is included. All aspects of the project are interdependent and work is ongoing in all areas, in light of anticipated content growth, new registry features, integration scenarios and applications. The report describes progress made thus far and includes a summary of anticipated developments in the funding period.

¹ <https://dev.bio.tools> (latest development version) or <https://bio.tools>

² <http://nar.oxfordjournals.org/content/44/D1/D38>

2. Technical overview

The portal software has two parts (Figure 1): the **server-side application** (or ‘backend’) and **client-side application** (or ‘frontend’). The backend includes a database that allows manipulation of its content, through actions such as retrieving, inserting, deleting and updating. The frontend is a web application which provides interfaces to the functionality that the backend offers, including a **query interface** and **registration interface**. The functions of the backend can be accessed via a **REST API**. This API is used by the client-side application, but can also be used by any other client application, created by a third party.

Figure 1 Registry architecture

Development of software features is based upon a **software description model** which uses the **EDAM ontology** and various miscellaneous **controlled vocabularies** defined within the model. The **registry content** (Section 3.4) is descriptions of bioinformatics software formatted according to the model. It has been added through a distributed curation effort as part of a broader **community build-up process** (Section 3.2, Appendix B), upon which the sustainable long-term maintenance depends.

We deploy two versions of the software as part of routine development:

- <https://dev.bio.tools> : development server including latest software features, for testing by end-users
- <https://bio.tools> : stable production server

We have developed eight key technical components in the reporting period:

- **software description model** (Section 3.3, Appendix C) defining the information the registry provides to support users to find, understand, compare, and select software resources (“discovery”), but also use and connect them in workflows (“interoperability”). The model is a formalised XML schema (biotoolsXSD). It supports the uniform description of key scientific, technical and administrative attributes using rigorous semantics and syntax.
- Versions 1.3 - 1.4 : advanced prototypes, v1.4 is currently supported by the development and production servers³
- Version 2.0 beta01 : candidate stable version
- **EDAM ontology** (Section 3.3.3) for scientific description of software including topics, operations, types of data, data formats and identifiers. Four versions (1.12 - 1.15) have been released.
- **controlled vocabularies** (Section 3.3.4, Appendix C) for miscellaneous technical details. Nine vocabularies have been developed.
- **registration interface** (Section 3.5.1, Appendix D.1) for manual creation of valid registry content and editing

³ <https://dev.bio.tools>

- **query interface** (Section 3.5.2, Appendix D.1) for registry end-users, including:
 - search bar providing advanced search functions
 - a summary view (default view of search results)
 - a grid view for comparing multiple tools
 - Tool Cards of pertinent information, on web pages at persistent URLs
- **back-end architecture** (Section 3.5.3, Appendix D.2) providing a MySQL database, a scheme for tool IDs and persistent URL, account management and administrator tooling
- **API** (Section 3.5.3.5) providing various search, retrieval and batch registration functions, including import and export in XML and JSON formats

The registry content is freely available to all under the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC BY 4.0), accordingly, members of the community may re-use the content for their own purposes and create their own interfaces tailored to their specific needs. EDAM and biotoolsXSD are licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International License (CC BY-SA 4.0), which afford the same freedoms, but require copies or adaptations of the work to be released under the same or similar licence as the original.

3. Community build-up process

A core function of ELIXIR is to organise and disseminate information about bioinformatics resources (broadly) and support the discovery and utilisation of these resources by end-users. Our aim - with community support - is to develop the bio.tools portal into a sustainable standard for dissemination of information about bioinformatics software⁴. To deliver a high quality, sustainable global portal that not only satisfies the needs of end-users but also is tailored to the requirements of providers, is a very hard, multi-faceted problem, beyond the reach of any one individual, project or institute. It was therefore necessary, from the outset, to take a community-based approach: most aspects have been developed in collaboration with major service providers, cataloguers and community projects. Community build-up has been a high priority. Our approach is very extensive and includes a combination of methods and products summarised below.

Hackathons are the primary vehicle for community build-up and collaborative development. A total of 11 events (Appendix B.1) have been run in the reporting period, of four types:

- **curation hackathons** gather resource providers from across the board, helping them to describe their software to a common standard and register it. They are further expected to critique the registry user interfaces. These hackathons provide a forum for knowledge exchange, outreach and collaboration.
- **resource hackathons** engage experts from a specific collection of tools and services, typically some organisation or community project, to identify their specific needs and bring the collection up to the ELIXIR standard⁵ and expose it in the registry.
- **thematic hackathons** engage experts in a specific scientific area to collate lists of key software, define terms for their description to improve EDAM, consolidate existing registry annotations, as well as register new resources within the theme, ensuring the portal initiative broadly satisfies the specific needs of that community.
- **technical hackathons** focus on ontology, software or other technical developments in support of curation of the registry, its technical development, applications and integration with other systems.

⁴ For a definition of what this includes, i.e. the scope of the registry see Section 3.2.1

⁵ i.e. including all information fields defined as mandatory within biotoolsXSD including EDAM annotations

Open governance models provide an informal framework by which the portal's senior and technical management translate ethos and policies into practices, procedures, and responsibilities within the distributed organisation, and contributions are recognised. bio.tools is led by the Danish ELIXIR node via two Technical Coordinators: Emil Rydza is leading the software development and Jon Ison is leading the collaborations and content, in close collaboration with the core developers of the registry and EDAM:

- bio.tools operates under a lightweight governance model⁶ (Appendix B.5), the heart of which is the 'registry-core' developers group: 29 people from 21 organisations, many of whom contribute on a voluntary basis.
- the EDAM governance model⁷ (Appendix B.6) includes the 'edam-core' developers group who have primary responsibility for delivering EDAM, with assistance from Editors and other contributors. There is also an Advisory Group and Steering Group.

Sifterapp (Appendix B.2) is used to manage all high-level tasks and is maintained by Jon Ison. It is open to anyone (upon request) and has 132 members including all of the registry-core group. It is the primary means for technical coordination: collaborators are encouraged to browse tasks, review priorities, make comments and add new tasks. It organises tasks into 10 strands for different facets of the project (everything from content, through to features and ideas for publications).

GitHub (Appendix B.2) is used for sharing code and data for all bio.tools-related projects. It is used for public discussion threads and to track fine-grained issues, and is the preferred way to make bio.tools feature requests, content suggestions, EDAM term requests, and bug reports.

JIRA is used to manage all low-level (implementation) software tasks and is maintained by Emil Rydza. It is open to anyone (upon request).

Community mailing lists (Appendix B.3) are available for general discussions, core developer discussions, announcements and support.

Monthly hangouts (Appendix B.4) with an open agenda provide a means for project updates and to respond to current critical needs. All are welcome.

Through the approach summarised above, we were able to:

- clarify the scope of the portal initiative (Section 3.2.1)
- clarify the aims and anticipated target audience and use-cases (Section 3.2.2)
- more broadly, gain insight on how practically to deliver the founding principles for the registry (Appendix A.1) established by the BioMedBridges project⁸
- refine the software description model (Section 3.3, Appendix C)
- gather requests for software features, ontology development and registry content
- set implementation priorities: anticipated new registry features are summarised alongside plans for content development (Section 3.6)
- identify possible future integration scenarios and applications
- build up awareness and a community around the portal and EDAM (Appendix B)

Much community feedback has already been addressed in the current portal software (Section 3.5), software description model (Section 3.3, Appendix C) and released EDAM versions (Section 3.3.3). The remaining feedback is tracked in sifterapp, GitHub and JIRA. The agile, community-driven, user-centered approach will continue to be applied to all aspects of the project as it moves from prototyping through the consolidation, expansion and integration phases.

⁶ <https://bio.tools/governance>

⁷ <https://github.com/edamontology/edamontology#governance-of-edam>

⁸ <http://www.biomedbridges.eu/>

3.1. Scope of the registry

bio.tools includes all types of **bioinformatics tools** - application software with well-defined data processing functions (inputs, outputs and operations). bio.tools includes simple tools with one or a few closely related functions, and complex, multimodal tools with many functions. Tools may be available for immediate use as online services, or in a form which a user can download, install, configure and run themselves. Each bio.tools entry describes a discrete, but possibly complex software entity. The types of tools (Table 1) defined in the candidate stable schema⁹ define the technical scope of the registry, i.e. the types of software that may be included¹⁰.

Table 1 Tool types

Tool type	User Interface tip / description	Interface type
Command-line tool	A tool with a text-based (command-line) interface.	CLI
Web application	A tool with a graphical user interface that runs in your Web browser.	GUI
Desktop application	A tool with a graphical user interface that runs on your desktop environment, e.g. on a PC or mobile device.	GUI
Suite	A collection of tools which are bundled together into a convenient toolkit. Such tools typically share related functionality, a common user interface and can exchange data conveniently. This includes collections of stand-alone command-line tools, or Web applications within a common portal.	CLI or GUI
Workbench	An application or suite with a graphical user interface, providing an integrated environment for data analysis which includes or may be extended with any number of functions or tools. Includes workflow systems, platforms, frameworks etc.	GUI
Database portal	A Web application, suite or workbench providing a portal to a biological database.	GUI
Workflow	A set of tools which have been composed together into a pipeline of some sort. Such tools are (typically) standalone, but are composed for convenience, for instance for batch execution via some workflow engine or script.	n/a
Component	A software component encapsulating a set of related functions, which are not standalone, i.e. depend upon other software for its use, e.g. a Javascript widget, or a plug-in that extends the function of some existing tool.	n/a
Library	A collection of components that are used to construct other tools. bio.tools scope includes component libraries performing high-level bioinformatics functions but excludes lower-level programming libraries.	API
Web API	An application programming interface (API) consisting of endpoints to a request-response message system accessible via HTTP. Includes everything from simple data-access URLs to RESTful APIs.	Web API
Web service	An API described in a machine readable form (typically WSDL) providing programmatic access via SOAP over HTTP.	Web API
SPARQL endpoint	A service that provides queries over an RDF knowledge base via the SPARQL query language and protocol, and returns results via HTTP.	Web API

All sources of application software are within scope, including commercial software, across all life sciences domains globally. Priority is given to simple tools and online services with open access and clearly defined functions, which are therefore readily combinable into functional workflows.

⁹ The software description model is implemented as an XML schema, see Section 3.3.

¹⁰ In the current portal software the notion of entry type and interface type are separate. Following user feedback and analysis, they will be conflated upon migration to the new stable schema.

Nonetheless, bio.tools also accepts complex services with many dependencies, and may also be used to manage collections which, for example, require logon or are have restricted access¹¹. Portal aims, target audience and use-cases

We envisage the portal providing a first port-of-call upon the search for bioinformatics solutions, and staging post for websites where resources can be researched further, used or downloaded. Our aims include ensuring that:

- scientists can find, understand and compare useful tools for computational experiments
- scientists are informed of the wealth of ELIXIR data resources and tools, and how they may be accessed
- bioinformaticians have clear clues as to what tools are compatible with what data types and formats, and thus which resources can most easily be chained into functional workflows
- developers can assess implementations of the available functionality, encouraging building on existing solutions over reinvention
- facility managers can see the status (nascent, mature, defunct) of a database, tool or service, and can assess its efficacy and applications during service design
- funders and reviewers have an overview of the productions at various hierarchical levels such as individual, institutional or even national
- information about the legacy of resources developments does not get lost
- software developers and service providers can contribute to the registry in simple but effective ways

The anticipated users thus include a spectrum of roles. To provide the convenience of a "one stop shop" at least the following criteria must be fulfilled:

- comprehensive coverage of the prevalent resources including major versions of tools
- consistent scientific, technical and provenance information required to support the practical discovery, use and interoperability of resources
- integration with the scientific literature and pertinent activities including benchmarking, monitoring and training
- sustained monitoring, validation and upkeep to ensure the corpus is non-redundant, up to date and correct
- adaptation to emerging needs, applications and technologies

Other, more specific use-cases (Appendix A.2) of the query interface have been carried through from BioMedBridges and extended.

In this deliverable report, we describe the essential social and technical groundwork. In future reports (D1.2 - D1.4) will evaluate the accomplishment of these aims.

3.2. Distributed community curation

Given our aims, the burden of curation and routine maintenance is onerous. Bioinformatics resource providers themselves are best placed and motivated to document their own productions, but given the diverse and complex biosoftware landscape, they require coordination and support. A major community-driven effort is required, backed by long term institutional commitments. We have published¹² a practical first step towards this end, that engaged enthusiastic individuals involved in biosoftware provision, integration and cataloguing, to maintain and share information about resources within their scope, thus, curation responsibilities are distributed.

¹¹ This is achieved by annotating the entry appropriately. Rendering of restricted access collections in the query interface is a work in progress but we anticipate such tools not to be visible by default.

¹² <http://nar.oxfordjournals.org/content/44/D1/D38>

The emphasis has been on bringing diverse documentation efforts into alignment and support this distributed curation effort, in a way that builds upon and supports local needs. Curation of the registry involves resource annotation, registration and updates of accessions, with concomitant ontology development. For this to be sustainable and - crucially - to yield high quality information that satisfies the needs of both bio.tools end-users and providers, the process must be simple and reliable. Yet high quality annotation can be difficult to achieve, especially when it is detached from the ontology development process. To mitigate the difficulties, we support individuals and institutions in a variety of ways:

- Direct assistance with curation, and particularly EDAM annotation including the creation of new terms, has been provided via mailing lists (Appendix B.3), sifterapp and GitHub (Appendix B.2) and by actively encouraging new EDAM Editors (Appendix B.6).
- A curation task-force, constituted of scientific domain experts, curators, and ontologists as required, has deployed to local sites in response to acute needs to assist partners. The main activity of the task force to date has been running the hackathons (Appendix B.1).

Through the support actions described, the curation effort expected from providers is reduced to a relatively small and maintainable level. We hope to attract and retain many new contributors and establish stable mechanisms for mass content import. This will be described in future deliverable reports as we move into the consolidation and expansion phases.

4. Software description model

The software description model is a formalised XML schema (biotoolsXSD) available from GitHub¹³:

- Versions 1.1 - 1.4 : advanced prototypes, v1.4 is currently in production¹⁴
- Version 2.0 beta01 : candidate stable version (Appendix C)

The model is an evolution of an early prototype developed by the BioMedBridges project¹⁵. Development of the model has been a recurrent theme of the hackathons and subject of many intense interviews and discussions. Thus, we are confident that the candidate stable version satisfies all major community requirements known at this stage, and provides a solid foundation upon which portal content, functions, integration and applications can be built in the project period. Specifically, it helps define those features which the registry interfaces, API and back-end architecture can or must support in the future (Section 3.6), in a rigorous logical and machine-readable format.

Encapsulating the model in an XML schema (XSD) has additional advantages: it allows for community development of the model to be loosely coupled to the portal software, and provides a means for a provider to validate content in XML format before submission, ensuring correct syntax, structure and completeness for a valid registry entry. Full schema documentation including example XML files for all versions is available from GitHub, or for v1.4 is also available at <https://bio.tools/schema>.

In order to provide rich but practical semantics covering the registry content, three actions were taken:

- Release of four new EDAM versions (Section 3.3.3) including refactoring to improve usability and additions to provide coverage.
- Revision of controlled vocabularies used in the production schema
- Creation of nine new controlled vocabularies (Section 3.3.4) used in the candidate stable schema

¹³ <https://github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsxsd>

¹⁴ <https://bio.tools>

¹⁵ <http://www.biomedbridges.eu/deliverables/33>

4.1. Software attributes

Attributes in the candidate stable schema, which is comprehensively documented including user interface tool tip suggestions, are described in detail in Appendix C.

The model supports the uniform description of key scientific, technical and administrative attributes using rigorous semantics and syntax. It defines a minimum annotation standard of 10 mandatory attributes (Table 2) for salient generic features, including specification of a tool's specific function(s) and primary inputs and outputs (Section 3.3.2). A total of 60 attributes are defined and organised into 12 logical groupings in the candidate stable version. To provide concise information, standard identifiers are used where possible, e.g. PubMed IDs for publications and ORCID IDs for people, and verbose information, for example, software documentation or citation instructions, are referred to by URL. Resources may be related to one another in various ways, for example, to define a new version of a tool, or an online service which provides an interface to a tool. They may also be tagged as belonging to any arbitrary collection. Hence, the dizzying complexity of bioinformatics software is reduced to collections of readily understandable functional units, put in scientific and technical context, including versions, distributions, deployments and interfaces for access and use.

Table 2 Mandatory attributes

Attribute	Description	Cardinality
Name	Canonical software name assigned by the software developer or service provider.	1 only
homepage	Homepage of the software, or some URL that best serves this purpose.	1 only
Short description	Short and concise textual description of the software function.	1 only
Tool type	A type of application software: a discrete software entity can have more than one type.	1 or more
Topic	General scientific domain the software serves or other general category. The URI and (optionally) term of EDAM Topic concept(s) are specified, e.g. "Proteomics", http://edamontology.org/topic_0121 .	1 or more
Operation	The basic operation(s) performed by this software function. The URI and (optionally) term of EDAM Operation concept(s) are specified e.g. "Multiple sequence alignment", http://edamontology.org/operation_0492 .	1 or more
Input data	Type of primary input data (if any). The URI and (optionally) term of EDAM Data concept(s) are specified, e.g. "Protein sequences", http://edamontology.org/data_2976 .	0 or more
Output data	Type of primary output data (if any): EDAM Data concept. The URI and (optionally) term of EDAM Data concept(s) are specified, e.g. "Sequence alignment", http://edamontology.org/data_0863 .	0 or more
Contact	Primary contact point of contact, e.g. a person, helpdesk or mailing list. One of email address or URL are specified.	1 or more
Publication	A publication about the software (if available). A DOI, PMID or PMCID is specified.	0 or more

Table 3 Attribute groups

Group	XSD element	UI tip / description	Cardinality
Summary	summary	Basic information about the software.	1 only
Function	function	Details of the function(s) that this software provides, expressed in terms from the EDAM ontology.	1 only
Labels	label	Miscellaneous scientific, technical and administrative details of the software, in terms from controlled vocabularies.	1 or more
Relations	relation	Details of relationships this software shares with other software registered in bio.tools.	0 or more
Command-line spec	commandLineSpec	Details of the command-line interface to a tool, if appropriate.	1 only
API spec	apiSpec	Details of the API to a service, if appropriate, including service endpoints.	1 only
Images	image	Details for virtual machine images or containers for the software.	0 or more
Downloads	download	Links to miscellaneous downloads for the software, e.g. source code.	0 or more
Documentation	documentation	Links to documentation about the software including training materials.	0 or more
Publications	publication	Publications about the software.	0 or more
Contacts	contact	Details of contacts for the software, e.g. developer or helpdesk.	1 or more
Credits	credit	Individuals and organisations that should be credited for the software.	0 or more

4.2. Model of tool function

The model of tool function in the candidate stable schema (Figure 2) is simplified: each software entity has one more tool functions, each of which performs one or more basic operations, and has zero or more primary input and/or output data, each of a specified type and supported format(s). Operation, data type and format are described in terms from EDAM; an EDAM concept URI and optional term (either the concept preferred label or synonym) are specified (Figure 3). An optional concise comment about the function as whole may be added, if not apparent from the software description and EDAM annotations. Execution-layer information, for example, command-line tool options or Web service endpoints, are modelled elsewhere in the schema, but are out of scope of this deliverable report.

Figure 2 Tool function in biotoolsXSD

Figure 3 Model of EDAM concept

4.3. EDAM ontology

EDAM¹⁶ is a simple ontology of well established, familiar concepts that are prevalent within bioinformatics, including types of data and data identifiers, data formats, operations and topics (Figure 4). EDAM provides a set of terms with synonyms and definitions - organised into an intuitive hierarchy for convenient use.

¹⁶ <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/23479348>

Figure 4 EDAM ontology

EDAM ontology development is use-case driven, the primary use-case being the ELIXIR Tools and Data Services Registry. Accordingly, new concepts and terms are added to provide coverage of the registry, in response to requests by the community, directly on GitHub, via the EDAM mailing list or during hackathons.

All EDAM versions are available for download¹⁷ and browsing from BioPortal¹⁸ or EMBL-EBI OLS¹⁹. Highlights of changes follow; see the online summary of changes²⁰ and detailed changelog²¹ for exact details of changes:

- **EDAM_1.15** - structural improvements and fixes including a clean-up of synonyms, new environmental omics and biodiversity terms, revisions to and additions of data formats, and simplification of concepts for data visualisation
- **EDAM_1.14** - miscellaneous additions and changes in response to user requests
- **EDAM_1.13** - simplification of Topic branch in response to requests for a smaller, more usable and thus also more sustainable set of topics, addition of new formats, addition and change to cover NGS tool packages
- **EDAM_1.12** - reorganisation of top-level Operation and Data concepts to make these branches more usable, new concepts for mass spectrum and NGS analysis, many concept deprecations and new synonyms

4.4. Controlled vocabularies

Nine new controlled vocabularies are defined in the candidate stable schema. They are standardised enumerations of terms (summarised in Appendix C):

- types of tool (command-line tool, Web application etc.)
- status such as maturity or financial cost

¹⁷ <https://github.com/edamontology/edamontology>

¹⁸ <http://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/EDAM>

¹⁹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/edam>

²⁰ <https://github.com/edamontology/edamontology/blob/master/changelog.md>

²¹ <https://github.com/edamontology/edamontology/blob/master/changelog-detailed.md>

- license
- programming language
- operating system
- types of relations by which one entry may be related to another, e.g. isNewVersionOf
- virtual machine image disk formats and containers
- types of downloads, documentation and publications
- roles that may be assigned to creditable entities

5. Portal content

5.1. Content summary

As of June 2016, the registry (Figure 5) includes 2,550 entries from a total of 283 contributors. These contributors include individual people (202, 15% of entries), institutional organisations (76, 44% of entries) and other registries and collections, including software packages (5, 41% of entries). The latest statistics including a list of named contributors are available from the portal website²². Contributions are included from institutes from almost every ELIXIR node, organisations beyond the ELIXIR network, e.g. the German Network for Bioinformatics Infrastructure (de.NBI²³), and other Research Infrastructures, e.g. INSTRUCT. A breakdown of the content by source is below (Figure 6). As expected, the major contributors include major European service provider institutes (e.g. Institut Pasteur, EMBL-EBI) and other catalogues and packages (e.g. BioConductor, EMBOSS), content from which has been imported *en masse*. There is however a significant “long tail” of providers from across the spectrum of, mostly, European bioinformatics. We are therefore confident that the registry already includes a reasonably representative subset of all the tools it should in due course be included. Much of this content was a result of a major outreach push including curation hackathons (Appendix B.1). An encouraging sign is that, in 2016 Q1 - Q3 the registry has seen a steady trickle of new, unsolicited contributions, *i.e.* is growing organically.

This initial content should be seen as a seed for the registry; real data that allowed us to validate and improve the model, ontology and portal software. Ongoing content quality improvements - crucially refactoring and extending the content to comply with the proposed stable schema - will be prioritised in the consolidation phase, and expansion of the registry in the expansion phase of the project, as we move towards more comprehensive coverage.

The registry content is available for download from the bio.tools portal²⁴.

²² <https://bio.tools/stats>

²³ <https://www.denbi.de/>

²⁴ <https://dev.bio.tools/api/tool/>

Figure 5 Registry content

Figure 6 Registry contributors

5.2. Content annotation

Content is annotated in terms from the EDAM ontology and various miscellaneous controlled vocabularies defined within biotoolsXSD. A description of the annotations is out of scope here and will be described in detail in a future deliverable report. The existing annotations will be extended and improved in due course, as part of the ongoing content quality improvements, with a priority given to publications, tool function, and software licences.

6. Portal software

The current development version²⁵ was a major rewrite of the production system²⁶ incorporating many improvements in response to end-user feedback, including:

- decoupling of notions of affiliation and account²⁷
- robust validation of content, including validation of content²⁸ without necessity to save it

²⁵ <https://dev.bio.tools>

²⁶ <https://bio.tools>

²⁷ The affiliation associated with registry entries have been retained as credits, and can be edited.

²⁸ Going beyond what is (and can be) encapsulated in the XML schema (biotoolsXSD).

- redesigned search bar (Section 3.5.2.1) with new backend search architecture
- redesigned “grid view” (Section 3.5.2.3)
- greatly improved performance (load-time in particular)
- support for unique tool IDs and persistent URLs (Section 3.5.3.2)
- improved account management (Section 3.5.3.3)
- administrator tooling (Section 3.5.3.4)
- new stable API (Section 3.5.3.5)

Once put into production, a whole raft of improvements and new features (Section 3.6) will be added progressively. The sections below mostly describe details in the development version.

6.1. Registration interface

Anyone with a bio.tools account can add or edit registry content. There are two options for doing so:

- manual registration via the bio.tools registration interface (described below)
- batch registration via API by submission of a file in JSON or XML

In either case, to be saved successfully, details provided must validate against the software description model as defined by biotoolsXSD and encapsulated by server-side application (Appendix D.2). The validation goes beyond what can be encoded within an XML schema, e.g. validity of EDAM concept URL annotations²⁹. An entry can also be validated without saving, for the convenience of users.

The client-side application provides a set of interfaces to simplify the creation and editing of valid registry entries. The main interface (Figure 7) is available to logged-in users. It has a number of tabs, each containing a number of fields that correspond to various software attributes. Whether a field is mandatory or optional, as per the biotoolsXSD definition, is indicated visually.

Figure 7 Registration interface

A simple widget (Figure 8) is provided to assist with EDAM annotations. The widget displays the relevant branch of the EDAM ontology as a tree, and allows a user to browse and search for

²⁹ i.e. the URL exists within EDAM and identified a non-deprecated concept

relevant terms. This widget has been adequate for creation of the seed content, however, far more sophisticated tooling is required, certainly for the expansion project phase.

Figure 8 EDAM annotation widget

Once complete, the software annotation can either be saved (and therefore immediately made public), or just validated to check for correctness, by pressing relevant buttons.

An adaptation of the registration interface is used for editing the information on existing entries. Some limitations are enforced, such as not allowing the user to change the unique ID of an entry (Section 3.5.3.2).

6.2. Query interface

The query interface consists of

- search bar providing advanced search functions
- a summary view - default view of search results
- a grid view for comparing multiple tools
- Tool Cards of pertinent information, on web pages at persistent URLs

These components are described in the sections below.

6.2.1. Search bar

Facilities to search the registry are available via the search bar (Figure 9). Searching can be performed over all the attributes recorded by bio.tools (everything), or on a selected attributes (currently name, topic, function, input, output and credits in the development server³⁰).

Figure 9 bio.tools search bar

When a search term is entered, a list of suggestion appears (Figure 10). The suggestions currently³¹ include software names, terms from the EDAM ontology (that existing resources have

³⁰ this list is not final and subject to ongoing work

³¹ this list is not final and subject to ongoing work

been annotated with) and credits. A search can be performed on the free text entered, while choosing one of the suggestions performs a filtering:

- Searching produces results that are contextually related to the search term, and are sorted based on relevance. The threshold for returning unrelated results is lower than when filtering.
- Filtering is more precise, removing results that are not closely related to the selected term.

Both approaches can be combined, and by adding more search and filter terms the result can be refined. With every additional search term entered, the available suggestions are limited to the results of the previous queries, *i.e.* after searching for ‘prediction’, entering an additional term will only display suggestions taken from existing entries that are related to prediction. Our testing has shown that most end-users expect such behaviour.

Search terms are added to the URL of the page automatically, which means that the URL, and therefore the search, can be sent and shared with others. Searching and filtering is provided by Elastic³², a powerful and popular search engine (see Appendix D2.2.5).

Figure 10 bio.tools search bar (drill-down)

6.2.2. Summary view

The results of a search can be browsed on the main page of the application. Just below the search bar there is a component that displays a list of search results. The list is paginated, displaying 25³³ resources at a time. The pages can be changed with a paginator available above the list. By default the list is sorted on ‘Score’ which is the relevance score returned by Elastic, however this can be changed to sort on other attributes. The search terms are highlighted in the results. By default the results are displayed in a summary view (Figure 11), with every resource represented with as a block containing information about that tool.

³² Elastic, <https://www.elastic.co/>

³³ 25 was chosen since it gives a good balance between performance and usability

Figure 11 Query interface (summary view)

6.2.3. Grid view

The view can be changed to a “grid view” (Figure 12), that is akin to a spreadsheet, where every row represents a tool, and each column contains information about an attribute. The displayed attributes can be chosen, and the selection is stored in the browser. Clicking on the name of a tool links to the corresponding Tool Card.

Name	Description	Function	Input	Output	
Proteinspector	Analysis of mass spectrometry proteomics quality control metrics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Protein sequence analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mass spectrometry data (Textual format) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Image (qcML) Data 	Columns: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Name Version <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Description <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Function <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Input <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Output <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Topic Resource Type
Peptide-shaker	Interpretation of proteomics identification results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Protein sequence analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mass spectrometry data (MGF) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Image 	
dig2	dig2 is a simple but flexible in silico digester of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Protein cleavage site prediction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tool name (FASTA) (FASTA search results format) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Proteo (Textu 	

Figure 12 Query interface (grid view)

6.2.4. Tool Cards

Each bio.tools entry is assigned a unique, persistent URI (Section 3.5.3.2) which resolves to an informative Tool Card (Figure 13) of essential information. These webpages are designed to provide an convenient and intuitive view of registry content for the busy end-user. The functions as well as inputs and outputs are presented in an easily viewable graphical manner.

SignalP v.4.1
<http://cbs.dtu.dk/services/signalp/>
 Prediction of the presence and location of signal peptide cleavage sites in amino acid sequences from different organisms.

Free with restrictions
 GNU General Public License v3
 Stable

Protein signal peptides Protein cleavage sites

```

  graph LR
    A[Sequence (FASTA)] --> B[Protein signal peptide detection  
Protein cleavage site prediction]
    B --> C[Protein features (GFF)  
Sequence report]
  
```

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 • PUBMED: 21959131
 • DOI: 10.1038/nmeth.1701

Figure 13 Tool cards

6.3. Back-end architecture

The back-end architecture includes

- back-end database
- scheme for tool IDs and persistent URLs
- account management
- administrator tooling

These components are summarised in the sections below.

6.3.1. Back-end database

MySQL is used as a back-end database with structure defined using data models. The Django framework is used and provides a database-abstraction API that allows for creating, retrieving, updating and deleting objects. For details see Appendix D.2.

6.3.2. Tool IDs and persistent URLs

Each bio.tools entry is assigned a unique identifier (`toolID`). By default this is identical to the tool name (although cleaned to be URL safe), and this can be edited by the user of the registration interface, before saving. Once registered, the `toolID` cannot be changed. These identifiers are transformed to unique, persistent URIs, resolving to informative Tool Cards (Section 3.5.2.4) of essential information. bio.tools URIs are human-readable and include the unique tool ID and provider-supplied, optional version information³⁴:

```
bio.tools/tool/{toolID}{version}
```

³⁴ In the current production server each version of the same software requires a different `toolID`. This behaviour is soon to be replaced with one where various versions of the same software share a common `toolID`.

When a new version of a tool is registered, the card for the obsolete tool is retained. Similarly, registered services which, for one reason or another, are no longer operational retain their URI. Hence, descriptions of legacy tools and services are archived. Our URIs represent a pragmatic approach to the problem of software identity, and can provide a recognised and impactful means to cite and trace resources, especially in the absence of a traditional publication.

6.3.3. Account management

Anyone with a valid email address can create a bio.tools account. The client-side application offers facilities (Figure 14) for creating accounts, and for logging in and resetting passwords. After requesting creation of a new account, bio.tools will send an email to the registered email address, with a confirmation link. Similarly, when resetting the password, bio.tools will send a password reset link to the submitted email address. Assuming that an account with that email address exists, the link will lead to a webpage that allows for entering a new password.

Please log in

Username / Email

Password

Log in

[Forgot the password? Reset it.](#)

[Don't have an account? Create one.](#)

Figure 14 User authentication

A registered, logged-in user can access a profile page (Figure 15) that displays information about their account, as well as list all the software registered under that account. Links to the corresponding Tool Cards are available.

elixir Tools and Data Services Registry

Home Add content Docs CBS

My profile

Username CBS

Email cbs@dtu.dk

My resources

Name	Version	Added	Last updated
GenePublisher	1.03	2 years ago	2 months ago
HMMgene	1.1	2 years ago	2 months ago
InterMap3D	1.3	2 years ago	2 months ago
MLST	1.7	2 years ago	2 months ago
NetAcet	1.0	2 years ago	2 months ago
NetAspGene	1.0	2 years ago	2 months ago

Figure 15 User profile page

6.3.4. Administrator tooling

The server-side application includes an admin panel - an interface that allows bio.tools administrators and trusted users to manage bio.tools content. The admin site allows to enter content that normally would not pass validation, and therefore is intended to be used only by trusted users, who are aware of the implications. The admin panel allows to alter all database contents of bio.tools, such as registered resources, user accounts *etc.*

Figure 16 Admin panel

Figure 17 Admin panel (editing)

6.3.5. API

All of the following operations (and more) can be accessed through the REST API:

- registering resources
- retrieving entire catalog of resources
- searching for content
- updating / deleting resources
- account operations
- retrieving statistics

Online documentation is available and offers a detailed description of the API capabilities:

http://biotools.readthedocs.io/en/latest/api_reference.html

7. Future Work

A summary of high-level tasks in the “bio.tools features” and “bio.tools content” strands of sifterapp that have been assigned “Critical” or “High” priority³⁵ are summarised in Table 4. In addition, a summary of planned bio.tools features is given in the sections below.

Table 4 Planned registry feature and content development

Tracker ³⁶	Task	Priority	Expected delivery date
bio.tools features	Content ownership / permissions model https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/93	Critical	2016 Q4
bio.tools features	Support for candidate stable schema https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/194	Critical	2016 Q4
bio.tools features	Subdomains https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/190	Critical	2017 Q1
bio.tools features	"Sandbox" function for intermediate registrations https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/107	Critical	2017 Q1
bio.tools features	Improved QA/QC process https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/117	High	2017 Q2
bio.tools features	Automated support for new EDAM releases https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/38	High	2017 Q2
bio.tools features	Improved search and filtering https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/37	High	2017 Q3
bio.tools features	Content monitoring and reporting https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/72	High	2017 Q3
bio.tools content	msutils.org import (238 tools) https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/28	Critical	2016 Q4
bio.tools content	SEQwiki import (700+ tools) https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/27	Critical	2016 Q4
bio.tools content	Registration of services from Node proposals https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/189	Critical	2017 Q1
bio.tools content	Clean-up EDAM Operation annotations https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/156	High	2017 Q1
bio.tools content	Clean-up EDAM Topic annotations https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/155	High	2017 Q1
bio.tools content	Refactor content assigning tools to primary providers https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/171	High	2017 Q2
bio.tools content	RNA analysis tools import (368 tools) https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/62	High	2017 Q2
bio.tools content	ExpASY tools import https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/33	High	2017 Q3
bio.tools content	Content quality review https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/195	High	2017 Q3

Content ownership / permissions model

In the current implementation only the “owner” (the original author) of a bio.tools entry can update an entry, *i.e.* edit its annotations, or delete an entry. This model will be replaced with one where

³⁵ Tasks of priority “Normal”, “Low” and “Trivial” are not shown.

³⁶ one of the 10 task strands defined in <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/>

ownership can be made public, or shared with specific account holders, in a similar way to Google documents. A technical proposal has been developed³⁷.

The (conflated) notion of affiliation and entry owner in the old system was removed in the development server. The anticipated new behaviour is that the entry owner annotates the credits for a tool, as per the possibilities defined in the candidate stable schema. All credited entities are considered contributors, with lists of tools credited a contributor and metadata available via subdomains and API endpoints (see above).

When annotating credits, an entry owner will be able to:

- credit an existing contributor from a global list
- add a new one, providing some metadata as per the biotoolsXSD credits definition. The newly created contributor is assigned a unique ID (`contributorID`), and is added to the global list of contributors.

In the development server we have a working and usable setup that implements parts of the above. The full solution will be rolled out in due course.

Subdomains

There have been multiple requests for local views of bio.tools content, providing a means for promotion of individual collections. The issues has been subject of much discussion and the settled proposal is - in the first instance - to support bio.tools subdomains, providing a “contributors view”: bio.tools homepage prefiltered to show all entries credited to that contributor, with (optional) minimal³⁸ customisation and branding, e.g., a logo, contributor metadata, and possibly bespoke default columns. A technical proposal³⁹ has been developed with subdomains of the type:

```
{contributorID}.bio.tools
```

where `{contributorID}` is the unique identifier of a bio.tools contributor (see below). Similar information available will be available via endpoints for contributors, e.g.:

```
bio.tools/contributor/{contributorID}
```

Support for candidate stable schema

We now have a candidate stable schema which will be supported in the portal software:

- back-end application update
- front-end application update
- content migration

The requirement in the first instance is to migrate existing content and support a prioritised subset of the new fields - a prerequisite to building new registry features that are now supported by the new model. While more than 2500 tools have been registered, annotations vary in richness.

³⁷ see <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/93>

³⁸ whatever can be achieved with the available resource, i.e. currently not custom features

³⁹ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1vDxejS7MWluSm8EXK3y7jCd39trEmitMhq8cGNodYQeA/edit#>

Consistent with the distributed curation model, the ongoing improvement of annotations will continue.

Improved QA / QC process

Additional Quality Assurance / Quality Control measures will include checks and reporting of:

- broken links
- duplicate homepage URLs
- use of top-level EDAM concepts
- use of deprecated EDAM concepts
- input, output or publication⁴⁰ not specified
- XML export validity check⁴¹

Additional checks may be added in light of a planned content quality review.

Automated support for new EDAM releases

The process of updating the registry for new releases of EDAM, which includes various checks and fixes, for example replacing deprecated terms with replacements indicated in EDAM, will be automated. This will ensure bio.tools keeps pace with EDAM developments; this being expected and requested by end-users.

"Sandbox" function for intermediate registrations

Several providers have partially annotated content and want to use the registration interface for community-based improvement. A registry "sandbox" allowing viewing and editing of such content could also boost content contributions: by preloading incomplete (therefore cheap) content, followed by mailout to tool owners requesting they complete the registration. This is a proven technique, for example in the case of BioPortal.

Improved search and filtering

Robust basic search functionality is provided by the search bar. This will be extended, in the first instance to:

- support for more fields
- support for more controlled vocabularies
- smart support for EDAM synonyms

Much more can and will be done, for example user experience evaluation and subsequent parameter optimisation of the search algorithm, support for boolean search operators *etc.*

Content monitoring and reporting

Registry statistics are already auto-generated. The monitoring and reporting needs will be enhanced to provide finer-grained details of content growth and change, to support the portal consolidation and expansion phases.

⁴⁰ these fields are mandatory where such information is available

⁴¹ a belts-and-braces check against biotoolsXSD; export should normally be valid

Appendix A: Founding principles

A.1 Founding principles

The design and long-term success of the registry is predicated upon 16 principles that were identified during the user-centered design process:

Purposefulness - The registry has two primary purposes; to help people discover software and use it. By “discovery” we mean to find, understand, compare and select. However, the registry does not aim to support “interoperability” of tools; the reason for this is that doing so would require careful and extensive modeling of dependencies and such modeling is out of scope.

Use-case driven - The registry should provide an “on-ramp” for the working bioinformatician and be a staging post for websites where tools and services may be researched in greater detail, used or downloaded. That said, the registry should be useful generally and support other roles identified by our market research, for example a scientist browsing the available offerings, a manager surveying the output of a grant, institute or infrastructure, a developer reviewing the state of art, and so on.

Generality - Many types of software and software interfaces will remain in use for the foreseeable future: downloadable analytical software with a command-line interface or desktop GUI, remote-access REST and SOAP-based Web services and Web UIs, covering all the bioscience domains and providing access to a vast array of biological databases. The registry - especially as a tool inventory for BioMedBridges - must cover this diversity, but focus on the prevalent types, notably Web UIs and data services.

Detailed - Considering the broad scope, the registry must concentrate upon the principal and common software features that are necessary to support the use-cases, without descending into excessively fine-grained details. To fulfill its purpose however and especially to allow comparison, the registry must provide information in sufficient detail and structure, which cannot conveniently be obtained from a Google search or cursory inspection of a provider’s website.

Practicality - Software manifests in a dizzying complexity of deployments, interfaces, wrappers, suites, libraries, packages etc. The registry must be practical and therefore expose software in a useful way, i.e. in terms of readily understood, consistent functional units. It must shield people from superfluous details whilst providing enough information to place a tool or service in context of the deployments, interfaces and collections in which it appears.

Comprehensiveness - In order to fulfill its purpose the registry *must* be comprehensive, include all prevalent databases, tools and services and obtain the widest coverage of the scientific domains as resources allow. A given resource must be fairly comprehensively detailed, as described above. This effort has to be distributed and involve the major tool providers, integrators and cataloguers, as well as individual developers and scientists.

Quality - The registry will face fierce competition. Success depends on goodwill engendered by solid Quality Assurance: it is of utmost importance that the registry stay relevant with continuous upkeep. The information must not be wrong or go stale and therefore must be validated, for example to ensure there are no broken links, invalid annotations or missing fields. Again, this can only be accomplished by the creation and support of a community and distributing the effort among its members.

Accessibility - Registry users will have high expectations and demand key information is put immediately at their fingertips, in an interface that is very simple and intuitive to use. The registry query interface must therefore be immediately accessible, highly streamlined and practical. The search and browse/query functions must be powerful, convenient to perform and quickly yield concise, relevant and meaningful results.

Consistency - The query interface must have a consistent look and feel and also return consistent and therefore comparable information. To that end we envisage all registry entries to be annotated with controlled vocabularies: EDAM for annotation of topic, function, data types and formats specific for the life sciences area, SWO for general software attributes, and others, whenever appropriate. This will allow for precise searching and consistent search results, taking the impact of the registry beyond merely finding tools: comparison, evaluation and interoperability will be greatly facilitated.

Compatibility - There are a multitude of relevant technologies and developments, including *ad hoc* catalogues and lists

of tools, formal registries, service description models and exchange formats, controlled vocabularies *etc.* The registry should, where possible and desirable, use, build upon and operate harmoniously with all of it. For example, we expect a variety of models, methods and formats for describing and documenting software will remain in use, and aim therefore to be compatible with these. Similarly for databases, our information model must for example be compatible with the core attributes of biological databases as defined by BioDBCORE.

Responsibility - We believe that tool and service data, as part of software documentation, is rightly the “property” of the developer or provider, or at least a responsible cataloguer. In so far as these enterprises are publicly funded, there is a responsibility to share information. We are therefore promoting this notion and encourage providers *etc.* to publish such data alongside their tools and services. In this spirit, we share the registry data and code, and open their development to anyone. Further, where software data are registered with us that are in scope of some other catalogue, we will forward the data and collaborate to ensure the catalogue incorporates it.

Sustainability - The registry effort must be sustainable in the long term with limited resources. Digital curation is, however, time consuming and costly. To minimise future maintenance costs, we are promoting a federated curation model which envisions key providers, integrators and cataloguers as the “primary citizens” that maintain and share information about the resources within their scope: curation responsibilities are federated. Rather than aspiring to maintain software information centrally, the registry serves as a collation or “snapshot” of the available information distributed on the Web. For example, the registry will import Web service descriptions from BioCatalogue and those of GRID-enabled software from EGI AppDB.

Collaborativeness - Success is predicated ultimately on the good will of enthusiastic individuals, working within the key institutes and infrastructures, to assume responsibility for the resources that they provide or care about. The primary challenge in the long term is therefore a social one: building and supporting a community to maintain a federated curation of information. We cannot do everything and so must encourage others to do “heavy lifting” in their specialised areas, for example BioCatalogue to process machine-readable service descriptions (WADL, WSDL, Swagger *etc.*)

Focus - The registry must remain focused on community requirements as gauged by workshops, mailing lists and other activities. “Mission creep”, even into important areas, must be avoided given the limited resources. For example, the registry will not, in the first instance, provide a tools forum with user ratings and comments, a community wiki, or become a software repository. Similarly, while service versioning and monitoring are important to the user the registry will not, in the first instance, implement a fully-fledged service monitoring framework, or anything else that is properly the provider’s responsibility.

Extensibility - The technical components, for example the registry query interface, underlying schema *etc.* should be extensible and adaptable by others for their own purposes. More broadly, the technical outputs of this initiative are, in principle, applicable to non-software entities. One could envisage for example an adaptation of the registry software to federation of information about community events or job announcements. Extensibility was therefore borne in mind in the design process.

Inclusivity - The requirement for a tool and data service registry is universal. Duplicated, wasteful efforts should be avoided. The registry - as a key component of the bioinformatics and biomedical infrastructure - therefore embraces all relevant individuals, projects, institutions and infrastructures from the outset, from individual developers to major projects and providers, regardless of whether they are officially associated with the research infrastructures within BioMedBridges.

A.2 Query Interface use cases

Query Interface Use Cases

The Query Interface was designed to answer the following questions determined by user experience analysis:

- I have this task in mind, what tools are there for it ?
- I have this data, what can I do with it?
- I need to generate some data, what tools are there ?
- I need a tool that reads or writes data in a specific format?
- I need mass access for a specific type of data, what databases are available?
- What resources are available in a general area, e.g. proteomics?
- What resources arose from a particular grant?
- What are the outputs of a particular research institute or infrastructure?

Appendix B: Community details

B.1 Hackathons

Here we list hackathons in which ELIXIR personnel participated⁴² in order to develop the portal. All events are listed online⁴³.

Type	Name	Date / location	Description
Curation	Registration of Tool & Data Services	Nov 2014, Lyngby, DK	Gathered representatives of institutes and key projects within ELIXIR and beyond. The participants performed a valuable pre-release <i>critique</i> of the Registry mechanism and interfaces, and added more than 300 resources to the content. tinyurl.com/registryhackathon
Technical	EDAM Development & Governance	Mar 2015, Lyngby, DK	Focused on EDAM technical maintenance and usability, and produced a mock-up of tooling to assure optimal usage of EDAM for registry curation. tinyurl.com/registryhackathon2
Thematic	Defining good practice for resource annotation and registry curation	Aug 2015 23-25	A three day workshop organised and financed by ELIXIR-EE aiming to identify relevant processes and good practice for the annotation and curation of resources for their integration into the emerging ELIXIR infrastructure, focussed on next generation sequencing (NGS) analysis and the SeqWIKI Resource Hub. tinyurl.com/registryhackathon4
Thematic	RNA analysis	Sep 23-25 2015, Copenhagen, DK	A thematic hackathon focussed on RNA analysis and seeking to establish an ELIXIR RNA Tools Consortium that the Registry can draw upon in the future. XXX
Curation	Registration of Tool & Data Services	Nov 4-6 2015, Brno, Czech Republic	The second in the series, will aim for representation in the registry of all ELIXIR nodes, including new partners from Spain, Netherlands, Sweden and Finland, and other key resources beyond ELIXIR. tinyurl.com/registryhackathon3
Technical	EDAM development heuristics	Dec 1-4 2015, Amsterdam, Netherlands	This hackathon aimed at preparing EDAM for scaling with registry growth. The focus was to enumerate EDAM development heuristics to ensure usability, identify desirable clean-ups, and to devise quality assurance methods, including usability benchmarking in different scenarios. It also included a thematic session focussing on protein structural biology and the WHAT-IF package. tinyurl.com/registryhackathon5
Resource	de.NBI EDAM Codefest	Jan 19-20 2016, Freiburg, DE	This hackathon, organised by University of Freiburg, will focus on 1) annotation of de.NBI tools and services, 2) ELIXIR Registry and registration process and 3) Publishing tools in the ELIXIR Registry. http://tinyurl.com/registryhackathon7
Resource	bio.tools @ Debian Med Sprint	Feb 4-7 2016, Lyngby, DK	Co-located with the Debian Med sprint: a resource hackathon focussed on curation and software development towards annotation and registration of tool packages from Debian Med. https://wiki.debian.org/Sprints/2016/DebianMed2016
Resource	Norwegian Tools & Data Services	Mar 16-18, 2016, NTNU Trondheim, NO	A hackathon bringing together representatives of Norwegian bioinformatics communities with the ELIXIR Tools & Data Services Registry, dedicated to the description and cataloguing of Norway tools and services, to boost their discovery and utility. XXX

⁴² most of the events were funded using EXCELERATE resources

⁴³ <https://bio.tools/events>

Resource	French Tools & Data Services	March 24-25, 2016, IFB, Gif-sur-Yvette	A hackathon bringing together representatives of French bioinformatics communities with the ELIXIR Tools & Data Services Registry, dedicated to the description and cataloguing of French tools and services, to boost their discovery and utility. tinyurl.com/registryhackathon6
Resource	Slovenian Tools & Data Services	Apr 8, 2016, Faculty of Medicine, University of Ljubljana, SI	A resource hackathon aimed at engaging the majority of bio-groups and institutions from Slovenia and to register as many national tools and services as possible. The event will follow the annual meeting of CFGBC consortium members XXX
Thematic	Metagenomics	April 7-8, 2016, EMBL-EBI, UK	Organised in collaboration with the GOBLET and the ELIXIR Training Platform. It included a session on annotation of metagenomics tools.
Technical	Tools, Workflows and Workbenches	May 18-20, 2016, Institut Pasteur, Paris	A hackathon bringing together developers from key technical projects from ELIXIR and beyond including: the ELIXIR Tools & Data Services Registry (bio.tools), workbench/workflow projects (CWL, Galaxy, Taverna, Arvados), bioinformatics container solutions and registries, and the EDAM ontology. tinyurl.com/registryhackathon8

B.2 Issue and task management

sifterapp (<https://biotools.sifterapp.com>) is used to manage all high-level tasks in the bio.tools orbit and is the primary means for technical coordination of ELIXIR EXCELERATE WP1. Tasks are organised into 10 strands of activity:

- Benchmarking & monitoring
- bio.tools content
- bio.tools features
- biotoolsXSD
- Docs & Web
- EDAM content
- Events & outreach
- Ideas
- Publications
- Tooling

GitHub is used for sharing code and data for all bio.tools-related projects. It is used for public discussion threads and to track fine-grained issues, and is the preferred way to make bio.tools feature requests, content suggestions, EDAM term requests, and bug reports:

- <https://github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsregistry/>
- <https://github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsxsd>
- <https://github.com/edamontology/edamontology>

B.3 Mailing lists

Community mailing lists are available at {listName}@elixir-dk.org:

- edam EDAM ontology general discussions (35 members)
- edam-core EDAM ontology core developers discussions
- edam-announce EDAM ontology announcements
- registry ELIXIR registry general discussions (149 members)
- registry-core ELIXIR registry core developers discussions
- registry-announce ELIXIR registry announcements
- registry-support ELIXIR registry support requests

B.4 Monthly hangouts

Monthly hangouts are run on the last Friday of each month. Technical representatives of the ELIXIR-DK partner institutes routinely attend and all are welcome. The hangouts have an open agenda and respond to current critical needs. See

- <http://biotools.readthedocs.io/en/latest/hangouts.html>

B.5 Registry governance

The registry has three tiers of governance under the leadership of the Danish ELIXIR node (Professor Søren Brunak, Head of Node):

- Registry Core
- Registry Contributors
- Registry User Group

Registry Core includes the technical and scientific experts at the heart of the development and curation of bio.tools. They are responsible for agreeing aims and general good practice. Priorities are set in a quasi-democratic way with the **content leader** (currently Jon Ison) or **software leader** (currently Emil Rydza) having the final say where necessary (in so far as this is meaningful). Registry Core members must either be funded, or have the intent and some bandwidth, to develop the registry in the long-term.

The governance model is described in detail online. For further information, including a list of members of the Registry Core group see:

<https://bio.tools/governance>

B.6 EDAM governance

EDAM follows a model with five tiers of governance:

- EDAM Core Developers
- EDAM Editors
- Contributors
- EDAM Steering Group
- EDAM Advisory Group

EDAM Core Developers are responsible for agreeing aims and general good practice, overseeing and approving developments and routine maintenance. The model is quasi-democratic with a leader (currently Jon Ison) having the final say where necessary. Core Developers must have the intent and some bandwidth to develop EDAM in the long-term. They have 3 primary responsibilities:

- Understand and uphold the EDAM principles
- Advocate EDAM
- Develop EDAM as bandwidth permits

EDAM very much welcomes new editors and contributors. Representatives of projects who plan to adopt EDAM are welcome to join the EDAM Advisory Group.

The governance model is described in detail online. For further information, including a list of members of the different governance tiers, see:

<https://github.com/edamontology/edamontology#governance-of-edam>

B.7 EXCELERATE stakeholders

Through a combination of the approaches described above and multiple face to face meetings we have identified the portal scope and requirements in light of other EXCELERATE Work Packages. Highlights of the outcomes are below and will be elaborated upon in future deliverable reports. Multiple threads of activity concerning this work is tracked in <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/>.

Work Package	Inreach action / outcome highlights
WP2: Benchmarking	Planning representation, storage and dissemination of results of tool performance benchmarking and technical service monitoring. These data will be stored in an external silo and exposed in bio.tools via call to silo API. biotoolsXSD has been extended with key attributes, e.g. links to test data, scripts and benchmarking publications. Discussions on bio.tools and EDAM requirements to support generic benchmarking framework, e.g. extensions required for annotation of storage of metadata for tool benchmarking datasets.
WP3: Data resources and services	Discussions around definition of, and metrics for, ELIXIR-branded services. Identification of additional, ELIXIR-specific metadata requirements including labelling of services. biotoolsXSD labelling and credit mechanism have been revised accordingly, and is extensible to anticipated requirements.
WP4: Technical Services	Discussions around scope of bio.tools with respect to “technical services”: bio.tools will not include hardware services such as compute and storage, however, all application software is in scope including images (possibly of complex workflows) available on cloud infrastructure. Data sharing collaborations have been established, e.g. bio.tools will provide software metadata for reuse by projects such as BioExcel. Bio.tools will also explore piloting the ELIXIR AAI once this is available.
WP5: Interoperability backbone	bio.tools is implementing the FAIR principles for software tools and services through a systematic and focussed curation effort. biotoolsXSD has been extended accordingly, e.g. by supporting links to software distributions, and the definition of relationships between unique tools and deployed services where they may be used. Work towards comprehensive coverage of data formats and data identifiers in EDAM is ongoing, for use in bio.tools and re-use by WP5. A model of data resource APIs and endpoints has been added to biotoolsXSD, and this work is being coordinated with the bioschema.org project with view to providing data resource annotation for community re-use.
WP6: Marine metagenomics Use Case	Many metagenomics tools have been added to bio.tools and new metagenomics concepts added to EDAM. WP6 have specific requirements for relating the tools used in analytical pipelines. biotoolsXSD has been extended with a new tool relationships model to support this.
WP7: Crop and forest plants Use Case	A key WP7 requirement is to support annotation of the compatibility of a given registered API with an ELIXIR-defined standard. This is supported in biotoolsXSD through an extension of the labelling model.
WP8: Rare disease Use Case	A key WP8 requirement, identified through discussions with partners from industry, is for bio.tools to include detailed information about software licensing. This is supported in biotoolsXSD through a comprehensive controlled vocabulary for software license, enablin (in due course) additional features in bio.tools, e.g. additional labelling of software licenses as “free”, “open source”, “GPL-compliant” etc.
WP9: Human-access controlled data	An ongoing collaboration with BBMRI will coordinate the curation and sharing of tools biobanking-relevant software tools. Other requirements are similar to those for data resource API and endpoints (as per WP5).
WP10: Capacity building and communities	Discussions are ongoing with respect to how expertise in software best practice - specifically software documentation - can be built up in a way that leverages and contributes to bio.tools development. One possibility for community building is through sponsorship of student bio.tools curation projects in high priority national nodes.
WP11: Capacity building and communities	Much discussion and ongoing work is focussed on forging links between the ELIXIR Tools and Training platforms, including 1) cross-linking of bio.tools and TeSS, 2) systematic annotation of tools of high priority to trainers, 3) thematic hackathons including tool and training communities and platform representatives, 4) surveying of tool usage and needs in training courses, 5) provision of training materials for bio.tools, 6) extension of biotoolsXSD for tool-specific training materials.
WP12: Management and operations	Discussions are ongoing with respect to how WP1 can leverage ELIXIR Hub to develop coordinated strategy in areas such as funding, and conversely how ELIXIR Hub can re-use WP1 output e.g. exposing key metadata for ELIXIR branded services on the ELIXIR website.
WP13: Communications, Industry and Community Engagement	WP1 has taken a leading role in outreach to the broader community, including community projects such as Galaxy, Debian and SEQanswers. and through multiple channels including international conference and social media. Discussions are ongoing with respect to how WP1 can better leverage ELIXIR Hub in these areas.

Appendix C: Candidate stable schema

C.1 Design considerations

The design considerations for the registry software description model resulted in a set of characteristics:

- *Purposefulness* - the model must support the primary portal use-cases, *i.e.* include information in support of discovery and practical interoperability of software.
- *Use-case driven* - priority is given to features required to support specific portal use-cases.
- *Generality* - the model is generally applicable, *i.e.* to all manner of application software as per the registry scope.
- *Detailed* - the model covers salient software features without descending into excessively fine-grained details, but with sufficient detail and structure necessary to support the use-cases. Specifically it supports ready comparison and presentation of tool information, which cannot conveniently be obtained from a Google search or cursory inspection of a provider's website.
- *Practicality* - the model includes attributes with high practical value for the day to day work of portal end-users: superfluous details are excluded.
- *Consistency* - the model supports the precise searches within portal returning consistent and therefore comparable information. To that end, EDAM and various controlled vocabularies are used
- *Extensibility* - the schema is extensible and adaptable; by us to cater for emerging requirements, and by others for their own purposes.
- *Conciseness* - Most data fields are ontology concept, standardised enumerations of terms (controlled vocabularies), URLs, or standard identifiers, helping to ensure the sustainable upkeep of the registry and supporting future integrations and applications.
- *Simplicity* - The schema is as flat (unstructured) as possible, ensuring ease of use.
- *Compatibility* - It is inevitable that many providers, integrators, and cataloguers will continue to use their preferred models, methods and formats for software descriptions, on local sites at least. The model is broadly compatible to support future integration scenarios.
- *Stability* - There is a great cost of mutating schema. We therefore plan to restrict breaking changes once per year in released stable versions (versions 2.x). This is assured given the very extensive prototyping and collaborative development of the model.
- *Free and open source* - to encourage reuse and new applications.
- *Community developed* - to ensure the matches various end-users needs.

The tables below summarise the software attributes included in the candidate stable schema (biotools-2.0-beta01). The tables correspond to the attribute groups (Section 3.3.1) in the model.

C.2 Summary

Attribute	UI tip	Description	Comment	Type	Cardinality
name	Canonical software name.	Canonical software name assigned by the software developer or service provider.		xs:token (restriction)	1 only

version	Software version number.	Version (typically a version number) of the software assigned by the software developer or service provider.		xs:token (restriction)	1 only
biotoolsId	Unique ID that is assigned upon registration of the software in bio.tools.	Unique ID that is assigned upon registration of the software in bio.tools.	The ID is a URL in the bio.tools namespace and reflects (normally exactly) the tool name and version: see http://biotools.readthedocs.io/ .	URL (restriction)	1 only
doi	Canonical Digital Object Identifier of the software.	Canonical Digital Object Identifier of the software assigned by the software developer or service provider.		xs:token (restriction)	1 only
shortDescription	Short software description : a single declarative sentence in the present tense stating the tool function. Do not include tool name.	Short and concise textual description of the software function.	A single declarative sentence in the present tense, providing a terse statement of the tool function. State what is done, i.e.operation, and primary inputs and outputs, but not how. Do not include tool name. See http://biotools.readthedocs.io/ .	xs:token (restriction)	1 only
description	Software description, e.g. a few sentences adapted from the software publication abstract or homepage.	Textual description of the software.	This can be a few sentences adapted from the software publication abstract or homepage.	xs:token (restriction)	0 or 1
homepage	Homepage of the software, or some URL that best serves this purpose.	Homepage of the software, or some URL that best serves this purpose.		URL	1 only
mirror	Mirror of an (identical) online service.	Mirror of an (identical) online service.	Mirror sites are most commonly used for database portals to provide reliable access to large downloads.	URL	0 or more
repository	Repository where source code, data and other files may be downloaded.	Repository where source code, data and other files may be downloaded.		URL	0 or more
socialMedia	A website used by the software community including social networking sites, discussion and support fora, WIKIs etc.	A website used by the software community including social networking sites, discussion and support fora, WIKIs etc.		URL	0 or more

C.3 Function

Attribute	UI tip	Description	Comment	Type	Cardinality
operation	Operation performed (EDAM operation).	The basic operation(s) performed by this software function (EDAM Operation).	An EDAM Operation concept URL and (optionally) term are specified, e.g. "Multiple sequence alignment", http://edamontology.org/operation_0492 .	Ontology concept (restriction)	1 or more
input	<i>Details of primary input data.</i>	<i>Details of primary input data.</i>			

input->data	Input data type (EDAM data).	Type of primary input data, if any (EDAM data).	An EDAM Data concept URL and (optionally) term are specified, e.g. "Protein sequences", http://edamontology.org/data_2976 .	Ontology concept (restriction)	1 only
input->format	Input data format (EDAM format).	Allowed format(s) of the input data (EDAM Format).	An EDAM Format concept URL and (optionally) term are specified, e.g. "FASTA", http://edamontology.org/format_1929 .	Ontology concept (restriction)	0 or more
output	<i>Details of primary output data.</i>	<i>Details of primary output data.</i>			
output->data	Output data type (EDAM data).	Type of primary output data, if any (EDAM Data).	An EDAM Data concept URL and (optionally) term are specified, e.g. "Sequence alignment", http://edamontology.org/data_0863 .	Ontology concept (restriction)	1 only
output->format	Output data format (EDAM format).	Allowed format(s) of the output data (EDAM Format).	An EDAM Format concept URL and (optionally) term are specified, e.g. "FASTA-aln", http://edamontology.org/format_1984 .	Ontology concept (restriction)	0 or more
operation data format topic->url	EDAM Operation Data Format URL.	URL of an EDAM Operation Data Format concept.	The URL must be in the EDAM Operation Data Format namespace, i.e. http://edamontology.org/operation_ data_ format_ .	URL (restriction)	1 only
operation data format topic->term	EDAM Operation Data Format term (preferred label or synonym).	An EDAM Operation Data Format term (preferred label or synonym).	The term must be either the preferred label of the concept or a synonym of this term, as defined in EDAM.	xs:token	0 or more
comment	General comment about function.	Concise comment about this function, if not apparent from the software description and EDAM annotations.		xs:token (restriction)	0 or 1

C.4 Labels

Attribute	UI tip	Description	Comment	Type	Cardinality
toolType	Type of tool. A tool may have more than one type reflecting its different facets.	A type of application software: a discrete software entity can have more than one type.	bio.tools includes all types of bioinformatics tools: application software with well-defined data processing functions (inputs, outputs and operations). When registering a tool, one or more tool types may be assigned, reflecting the different facets of the software being described. For an explanation of valid values see github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsxsd .	enum (see below)	1 or more
topic	Scientific topic (EDAM Topic).	General scientific domain the software serves or other general category. The URI and (optionally) term of EDAM Topic concept(s) are specified.	An EDAM Format concept URL and (optionally) term are specified, e.g. "Proteomics", http://edamontology.org/topic_0121 .	Ontology concept (restriction)	1 or more
topic->url	EDAM Topic URL.	URL of an EDAM Topic concept.	The URL must be in the EDAM Topic namespace, i.e. http://edamontology.org/topic_ .	URL (restriction)	1 only

topic->term	EDAM Topic term (preferred label or synonym).	An EDAM Topic term (preferred label or synonym).	The term must be either the preferred label of the concept or a synonym of this term, as defined in EDAM.	xs:token	0 or more
goTermID	Gene Ontology (GO) term ID.	Gene function including molecular function, cellular component and biological process. Miscellaneous ontology annotation. The ID of Gene Ontology (GO) concept(s) are specified.	A GO concept ID is specified, e.g. "GO:0005125". Gene Ontology (GO) covers biological concepts and provides terms to describe gene function, including molecular function (molecular activities of gene products), cellular component (where gene products are active) and biological process (pathways and larger processes made up of the activities of multiple gene products).	xs:token (restriction)	0 or more
soTermID	Sequence Ontology (SO) term ID.	Features which can be located on a biological sequence. The ID of Sequence Ontology (SO) concept(s) are specified.	A SO concept ID is specified, e.g. "SO:0000147". Sequence Ontology (SO) provides terms to describe features which can be located on a biological sequence. SO includes biological features (e.g. binding site and exon) are those which are defined by their disposition to be involved in a biological process; biomaterial features (e.g. aptamer and PCR product) intended for use in an experiment and experimental features (the result of an experiment). The biological features are most relevant to software annotation.	xs:token (restriction)	0 or more
taxId	NCBI taxonomic group.	NCBI taxonomy ID of taxonomic group the software (particularly database portals) caters for.	The Taxonomy ID (TaxID or taxon number), e.g. "9606" is a stable unique identifier for each taxonomic group in the NCBI Taxonomy Browser. The TaxID is seen in the GenBank records under feature source.	xs:token (restriction)	0 or more
operatingSystem	Operating system supported by a downloadable software package.	The operating system supported by a downloadable software package.	For an explanation of valid values see github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsxsd .	enum (see below)	0 or more
language	Source code language.	Name of programming language the software source code was written in.	For an explanation of valid values see github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsxsd .	enum (see below)	0 or more
license	Software or data usage license.	Software or data usage license.	For an explanation of valid values see github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsxsd .	enum (see below)	0 or 1
status	Tag describing the software status.	Label describing miscellaneous status of the software.	For an explanation of valid values see github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsxsd .	enum (see below)	0 or more
collection	bio.tools ID of a software collection that the software has been assigned.	bio.tools ID of a software collection that the software has been assigned.	The ID is a URL in the bio.tools namespace and is assigned upon creation of the collection in bio.tools: see http://biotools.readthedocs.io/ . Collections may be created for some other registry, catalogue, WIKI etc. where this tool is described, or for any arbitrary purpose.	URL (restriction)	0 or more

C.4.1 Tool types

Tool type	UI tip / description	Interface type
Command-line tool	A tool with a text-based (command-line) interface.	CLI

Web application	A tool with a graphical user interface that runs in your Web browser.	GUI
Desktop application	A tool with a graphical user interface that runs on your desktop environment, e.g. on a PC or mobile device.	GUI
Suite	A collection of tools which are bundled together into a convenient toolkit. Such tools typically share related functionality, a common user interface and can exchange data conveniently. This includes collections of stand-alone command-line tools, or Web applications within a common portal.	CLI or GUI
Workbench	An application or suite with a graphical user interface, providing an integrated environment for data analysis which includes or may be extended with any number of functions or tools. Includes workflow systems, platforms, frameworks etc.	GUI
Database portal	A Web application, suite or workbench providing a portal to a biological database.	GUI
Workflow	A set of tools which have been composed together into a pipeline of some sort. Such tools are (typically) standalone, but are composed for convenience, for instance for batch execution via some workflow engine or script.	n/a
Component	A software component encapsulating a set of related functions, which are not standalone, i.e. depend upon other software for its use, e.g. a Javascript widget, or a plug-in that extends the function of some existing tool.	n/a
Library	A collection of components that are used to construct other tools. bio.tools scope includes component libraries performing high-level bioinformatics functions but excludes lower-level programming libraries.	API
Web API	An application programming interface (API) consisting of endpoints to a request-response message system accessible via HTTP. Includes everything from simple data-access URLs to RESTful APIs.	Web API
Web service	An API described in a machine readable form (typically WSDL) providing programmatic access via SOAP over HTTP.	Web API
SPARQL endpoint	A service that provides queries over an RDF knowledge base via the SPARQL query language and protocol, and returns results via HTTP.	Web API

C.4.2 Status

Status type	UI tip / description
Mature	Software that is generally considered to fulfill several of the following: secure, reliable, actively maintained, fully featured, proven in production environments, has an active community, and is described or cited in the scientific literature.
Obsolete	Software which is no longer in common use, deprecated by the provider, superseded by other software, replaced by a newer version etc.
Free of charge	Software which available for use by all, with full functionality, at no monetary cost to the user.
Free of charge (with restrictions)	Software which is available for use at no monetary cost to the user, but possibly with limited functionality, usage restrictions, or other limitations.
Commercial	Software which you have to pay to access.
Proprietary	Software for which the software's publisher or another person retains intellectual property rights—usually copyright of the source code, but sometimes patent rights.
Freeware	Proprietary software that is available for use at no monetary cost. In other words, freeware may be used without payment but may usually not be modified, redistributed or reverse-engineered without the author's permission.
ELIXIR Service	The software is an official ELIXIR service including Node-funded Services (i.e. services included in the Service Delivery Plan of an ELIXIR Node) and Commissioned Services (services commissioned by ELIXIR Hub and carried out by ELIXIR nodes).
Open access	An online service which is available for use to all, but possibly requiring user accounts / authentication.

Restricted access	An online service which is available for use to a restricted audience, e.g. members of a specific institute.
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C.4.3 License

A list of valid terms for software license is available online⁴⁴. Based on the specified license a label is attached to the tool.

Label	UI tip / description
Open-source	Software is made available under a license approved by the Open Source Initiative (OSI). The software is distributed in a way that satisfies the 10 criteria of the Open Source Definition maintained by OSI (see https://opensource.org/docs/osd). The source code is available to others.
Free software	Free as in “freedom” not necessarily free of charge. Software is made available under a license approved by the Free Software Foundation (FSF). The software satisfies the criteria of the Free Software Definition maintained by FSF (see http://www.gnu.org/philosophy/free-sw.html). The source code is available to others.
Free and open source	Software is made available under a license approved by both the Open Source Initiative (OSI) and the Free Software Foundation (FSF), and satisfies the criteria of the OSI Open Source Definition maintained (https://opensource.org/docs/osd) and the FSF Free Software Definition (http://www.gnu.org/philosophy/free-sw.html). Such software ensures users have the freedom to run, copy, distribute, study, change and improve the software. The source code is available to others.
Copyleft	Software is made available under a license designated as “copyleft” by the Free Software Foundation (FSF). The license ensures such software is free and that all modified and extended versions of the program are free as well. Free as in “freedom” not necessarily free of charge, as per the Free Software Definition maintained by FSF (see http://www.gnu.org/philosophy/free-sw.html).

C.4.4 Language

A list of valid terms covering most of all common programming languages is available online⁴⁵.

C.4.5 Operating system

Label	UI tip / description
Linux	A Unix-like and mostly POSIX-compliant computer operating system (OS) assembled under the model of free and open-source software development and distribution.
Windows	Any of the metafamily of graphical operating systems developed, marketed, and sold by Microsoft.
Mac	Any of the Mac OS X series of Unix-based graphical interface operating systems (OS) developed and marketed by Apple Inc.

C.5 Relations

Attribute	UI tip	Description	Comment	Type	Cardinality
biotoolsId	bio.tools ID of an existing bio.tools entry which this software is related to.	bio.tools ID of an existing bio.tools entry which this software is related to.	Relations may only be defined between registered software.	URL (restriction)	1 only
type	Type of relation between this and another registered software.	Type of relation between this and another registered software.	Certain relations may only be defined between certain types of tool. For an explanation of valid values see github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsxsd .	enum (see below)	1 only

⁴⁴ <https://github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsxsd>

⁴⁵ <https://github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsxsd>

C.5.1 Relation types

Relation	Inverse	UI tip / description
isNewVersionOf	hasNewVersion	The software is a new version of an existing software, typically providing new or improved functionality.
isInterfaceTo	hasInterface	The software provides a user interface to some other software without changing or extending its basic functionality.
uses	usedBy	The software uses the functions of some other software under the hood, e.g. invoking a command-line tool or calling a Web API, Web service or SPARQL endpoint to perform its function.
extends	extendedBy	The software extends, restricts or improves (somehow) the functionality or performance of another software. Includes adaptation and reimplementations of existing tools.
includes	includedIn	A workbench, toolkit or workflow includes some other, independently available, software.

C.5.2 Relation constraints

Type	Relation	Type	Description
TYPE_X	<i>isNewVersionOf</i> <i>extends</i>	TYPE_X	A software of any given type may be defined as a new version, or an extension, of a software of the same type.
Command line tool Web application Desktop application	<i>extends</i>	Command line tool Web application Desktop application	Software under one interface may extend the functionality of that with another type of interface.
Command line tool Web application Desktop application Suite Workbench Database portal Web API Web service	<i>isInterfaceTo</i> <i>uses</i>	Command line tool Suite Workflow Web API Web service SPARQL endpoint	Various software use or provide an interface to other types of software.
Workflow	<i>uses</i>	Command line tool Suite Workflow Web API Web service SPARQL endpoint	A workflow may use various types of software.
Component	<i>extends</i>	Command line tool Web application Desktop application Workbench Suite	A component extends the functionality of some other software
Library	<i>includes</i>	Component	
Suite	<i>includes</i>	Command line tool Web application Desktop application Workflow	

C.6 Command-line spec

Attribute	UI tip	Description	Comment	Type	Cardinality
syntax	Command-	A summary of the command-line	The value is text with optional	xs:token	1 only

	line tool syntax.	syntax for the tool.	markdown, see https://github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsxsd .	(restriction)	
summary	Command-line tool summary.	A textual summary accompanying the command-line syntax.	The value is text with optional markdown, see https://github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsxsd .	xs:token (restriction)	0 or 1
<i>option</i>	<i>Command-line tool option.</i>	<i>Details for an option to a command-line tool.</i>		-	<i>0 or more</i>
option -> syntax	Command-line tool option syntax.	A summary of the command-line syntax for specifying a tool option.	The value is text with optional markdown, see https://github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsxsd .	xs:token (restriction)	1 only
option -> summary	Command-line tool option summary.	A textual summary accompanying a command-line option syntax.	The value is text with optional markdown, see https://github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsxsd .	xs:token (restriction)	1 only

C.7 API spec

Attribute	UI tip	Description	Comment	Type	Cardinality
baseURL	Base URL of online service.	The base URL of a service, upon which one or more service endpoints are hung.		URL	1 only
<i>endpoint</i>	<i>Details of an endpoint to a service.</i>	<i>Details of an endpoint to a service, i.e. a URL that can be used to invoke a particular function of a service.</i>		-	<i>1 or more</i>
endpoint -> httpMethod	Endpoint HTTP method.	HTTP method used by the endpoint.		enum (see below)	1 only
endpoint -> urlTemplate	Template for a URL fragment, which when appended to the base URL, defines the syntax of a valid resolvable URL. The template can include parameters that must be substituted before the URL is resolved.	Template for a URL fragment, which when appended to the base URL, defines the syntax of a valid resolvable URL. The template can include parameters that must be substituted before the URL is resolved.	The value is text adhering to a strict syntax, see https://github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsxsd .	xs:token (restriction)	1 only
endpoint-> summary	Summary of service endpoint.	A textual summary of a service endpoint.	The value is text with optional markdown, see https://github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsxsd .	xs:token (restriction)	1 only
<i>endpoint-> output</i>	<i>Endpoint output.</i>	Details of output data provided by the endpoint.		-	<i>1 only</i>
endpoint->output-> data	Output data type (EDAM data).	Type of output data, if any (EDAM Data).	An EDAM Data concept URL and (optionally) term may be specified, e.g. "Sequence alignment", http://edamontology.org/data_0863 .	Ontology concept (restriction)	1 only
endpoint->output-> format	Output data format (EDAM format).	Possible format(s) of the output data (EDAM Format).	An EDAM Format concept URL and (optionally) term may be specified, e.g. "FASTA-aln", http://edamontology.org/for	Ontology concept (restriction)	0 or more

			mat_1984.		
<i>parameter</i>	<i>A query string parameter in the template URL that that must be substituted before the URL is resolved.</i>	<i>A query string parameter in the template URL that that must be substituted before the URL is resolved.</i>		-	<i>0 or more</i>
parameter->urlTemplateFragment	Fragment from the URL template for a parameter, which is replaced by some value when the service is called.	A fragment from the URL template corresponding to a URL parameter, which is replaced by some value when the service is called.	The value is text adhering to a strict syntax, see https://github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsxsd .	xs:token (restriction)	1 only
parameter->data	Parameter data type (EDAM data).	Type of data (EDAM Data) of a parameter of an endpoint.	An EDAM Data concept URL and (optionally) term may be specified, e.g. "UniProt accession", http://edamontology.org/data_3021 .	Ontology concept (restriction)	1 only
parameter->comment	Comment about parameter.	A comment about a parameter of an endpoint.		xs:token (restriction)	1 only

C.8 Images

Attribute	UI tip	Description	Comment	Type	Cardinality
url	Link to virtual machine (VM) image or container file.	Link to a download of a virtual machine (VM) image or container file, or a repository where this file may be downloaded.		URL	1 only
diskFormat	Virtual machine image disk format.	The disk format of a virtual machine image is the format of the underlying disk image. Virtual appliance vendors have different formats for laying out the information contained in a virtual machine disk image.	For valid values see github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsxsd .	enum (see below)	0 or 1
containerFormat	Virtual machine container format. A value of 'bare' should be specified if there is no container or metadata envelope for the image.	The container format indicates whether the virtual machine image is in a file format that also contains metadata about the actual virtual machine.	For valid values see github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsxsd . A value of 'bare' should be specified if there is no container or metadata envelope for the image.	enum (see below)	0 or 1

C.8.1 Disk format

Disk format	UI tip / description
aki	An Amazon kernel image
ami	An Amazon machine image
ari	An Amazon ramdisk image
iso	An archive format for the data contents of an optical disc, such as CD-ROM
qcow2	Supported by the QEMU emulator that can expand dynamically and supports Copy on Write
raw	An unstructured disk image format; if you have a file without an extension it is possibly a raw format

vdi	Supported by VirtualBox virtual machine monitor and the QEMU emulator
vhd	The VHD disk format, a common disk format used by virtual machine monitors from VMware, Xen, Microsoft, VirtualBox, and others
vmdk	Common disk format supported by many common virtual machine monitors

C.8.2 Container formats

Container format	UI tip / description
aki	An Amazon kernel image
ami	An Amazon machine image
ari	An Amazon ramdisk image
bare	The image does not have a container or metadata envelope
docker	A docker container format
ovf	The OVF container format

C.9 Downloads

Attribute	UI tip	Description	Comment	Type	Cardinality
url	Download link.	Link to download (or repo providing a download) for the tool.		URL	1 only
type	Download type.	Type of download that is linked to.	For an explanation of valid values see github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsxsd .	enum (see below)	1 only
comment	Comment about the download.	Comment about the download.		xs:string (restriction)	0 or more

C.9.1 Download types

Type	UI type / description
Source code	Link to a download of source code or to a repository where the source code may be downloaded.
Binaries	Link to a download of source code or to a repository where the source code may be downloaded.
Test data	Link to a download of data for testing the software is working correctly, or a repository where such test data may be downloaded.
Test script	Link to a download of a script used for testing whether the software is working correctly, or a repository where such a script may be downloaded.
Debian package	Link to information and downloads for the Debian package for the tool.
Package (other)	Link to information and downloads for a software package (other than Debian) for the tool.
Biological data	Link to a download of biological data or a web page on a database portal where such data may be downloaded.
Galaxy wrapper	Link to a download of a Galaxy tool config file (wrapper) for the software, or a repository where this file may be downloaded.
CWL file	Link to a download of a Common Workflow Language (CWL) file for the software, or a repository where this file

	may be downloaded.
Taverna wrapper	Link to a download of a workbench configuration file (other than Galaxy wrappers and CWL files) for the software, or a repository where this file may be downloaded.
Tool wrapper (other)	Link to a download of a workbench config file (wrapper) for the software, or a repository where this file may be downloaded.
Icon	Link to a download of an icon for the software, or a web page where an icon may be downloaded.

C.10 Documentation

Attribute	UI tip	Description	Comment	Type	Cardinality
url	Documentation link.	Link to documentation on the web for the tool.		URL	1 only
type	Documentation type.	Type of documentation that is linked to.	For an explanation of valid values see github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsxsd .	enum (see below)	1 only
comment	Comment about the documentation.	Comment about the documentation.		xs:string (restriction)	0 or more

C.10.1 Documentation types

Type	UI type / description
API specification	Machine-readable API specification e.g. WSDL file.
API documentation	Human-readable API documentation.
Terms of use	Rules that one must agree to abide by in order to use a service.
Citation instructions	Information on how to correctly cite use of the software.
Manual	Information on how to use the software.
Training material	Online training material such as text on a Web page, a presentation, video, tutorial etc.
Other	Some other type of documentation not listed in biotoolsXSD.

C.11 Publications

Attribute	UI tip	Description	Comment	Type	Cardinality
pmcid	PubMed Central Identifier.	PubMed Central Identifier (PMCID) of a publication about the software.		xs:token (restriction)	1 only
pmid	PubMed Identifier.	PubMed Identifier (PMID) of a publication about the software.		xs:token (restriction)	1 only
doi	Digital Object Identifier.	Digital Object Identifier (DOI) of a publication about the software.		xs:token (restriction)	1 only
type	Type of publication.	Type of publication.	For an explanation of valid values see github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsxsd .	enum (see below)	0 or 1

C.11.1 Publication types

Publication type	UI tip / description
primary	The principal publication about the software itself; the article to cite when acknowledging use of the software.
benchmark	A publication which assessed the performance of the software.
other	A publication about the software but not the primary publication or a benchmark study.

C.12 Contacts

Attribute	UI tip	Description	Comment	Type	Cardinality
name	Name of contact.	Name of contact.		xs:token (restriction)	1 only
email	Email address of contact.	Email address of contact.		email address	1 only
url	URL of contact.	URL of contact.		URL	1 only
tel	Telephone number of contact.	Telephone number of contact.		xs:token (restriction)	1 only
type	Role of contact.	Type or role of contact.	See github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsxsd .	enum (see below)	1 only

C.12.1 Contact types

Role	UI tip / description
Developer	Author of the software source code.
Maintainer	Maintainer of a mature software providing packaging, patching, distribution etc.
Provider	Institutional provider of an on-line service.
Helpdesk	A helpdesk providing support in use of the software.
Mailing list	A mailing list for general discussion about the software.

C.13 Credits

Attribute	UI tip	Description	Comment	Type	Cardinality
gridId	GRID ID of organisation.	Unique identifier (GRID ID) of an organisation that is credited.	Global Research Identifier Database (GRID) IDs provide a persistent reference to information on research organisations, see https://www.grid.ac/ .	xs:token (restriction)	1 only
orcidId	ORCID iD of person.	Unique identifier (ORCID iD) of a person that is credited.	Open Researcher and Contributor IDs (ORCID IDs) provide a persistent reference to information on a researcher, see http://orcid.org/ .	xs:token (restriction)	1 only
name	Name of credited entity.	Name of the entity that is credited.	Not needed if an ID is specified.	xs:token (restriction)	0 or 1

url	URL for credited entity.	URL for the credited entity, e.g. homepage of an institute.	Not needed if an ID is specified.	URL	0 or 1
entity	Type of entity that is credited.	Type of entity that is credited.	Not needed if an ID is specified. For an explanation of valid values see github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsxsd .	enum (see below)	0 or 1
role	Role performed by credited entity.	Role performed by credited entity.	For an explanation of valid values see github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsxsd .	enum (see below)	0 or 1
comment	A comment about the credit.	A comment about the credit.	This can elaborate on the contribution of the credited entity.	xs:token (restriction)	0 or 1

C.13.1 Creditable entities

Entity	UI tip / description
Person	Credit of an individual.
Project	Credit of a community software project not formally associated with any single institute.
Division	Credit of or a formal part of an institutional organisation, e.g. a department, research group, team, etc
Institute	Credit of an organisation such as a university, hospital, research institute, service center, unit etc.
Consortium	Credit of an association of two or more institutes or other legal entities which have joined forces for some common purpose. Includes Research Infrastructures (RIs) such as ELIXIR, parts of an RI such as an ELIXIR node etc.
Funding agency	Credit of a legal entity providing funding for development of the software or provision of an online service.

C.13.2 Creditable roles

Role	UI tip / description
Lead developer	Principal author of the software source code, taking a leading role in its production.
Developer	Contributor to the original software source code, but not a leading author.
Maintainer	Maintainer of a mature software providing packaging, patching, distribution etc.
Provider	Institutional provider of an on-line service.
Contributor	Some other role in software production or service delivery including design, deployment, system administration, evaluation, testing, documentation, training, user support etc.

Appendix D: Software architecture

D.1 Client-side application

The client-side application provides interfaces to the functionality offered by the server-side application (Appendix D.2).

D.1.1 Overview

The client-side application is a single-page application⁴⁶ (SPA) written in Javascript using AngularJS⁴⁷. AngularJS is a framework that uses the Model View Controller (MVC) architectural pattern. The pattern divides the application into three interconnected parts, with the intention to separate business logic, data model and the presentation layer. This approach fulfills the principle of separation of concern or segregation of duties. The UI look is created using Bootstrap⁴⁸, a popular HTML / CSS framework.

Figure 18 Client-side application architecture

D.1.2 Application

The structure of the application is based on the best practices for writing AngularJS applications. The application is made up of separate components (view-controller pairs, directives etc) placed within states, and working on data provided by services and factories.

⁴⁶ *i.e.* a [web application](#) or [web site](#) that fits on a single [web page](#) with the goal of providing a more fluid user experience similar to a desktop application

⁴⁷ AngularJS, <https://angularjs.org/>

⁴⁸ Bootstrap, <http://getbootstrap.com/>

Figure 19 Client-side application components

D1.2.1 Services

In AngularJS, services correspond to the 'model' in MVC. Services are used to help organise and share data and data related functions across the application. Services are the components capable of communicating with external APIs (such as the bio.tools API) to retrieve and send data as well as providing methods to communicate data across the controllers in a consistent way. They are responsible for the business logic of the application. Services are singletons that can be accessed from any other component: controller, directive *etc.*

D1.2.2 Views

Views provide the presentation layer of an application. In other words they are what a user sees and can interact with. Views in AngularJS are created using templates written in HTML. Views usually have a controller tied to them, which controls all but the simplest logic inside the view, as well as provides the view with data from the model.

D1.2.3 Controllers

The role of controllers in Angular is to expose data to a view, and to add functions that contain logic to enhance view behavior. Controllers tie views with services. When the user alters data in the view, it's the controller's responsibility to update the model (through a service). And the other way around, if the data in the model changes, the controller is responsible for updating the view. Controllers can also define APIs to communicate with other controllers.

D1.2.4 States

States are functionality added by the UI-Router⁴⁹ AngularJS library. A state is the top most element visible in a web application and it generally corresponds to a page. A state has a URL where it can be accessed, a view and a controller. The view can contain several other components, including other states. States and their nesting provide the top level structure of an application. bio.tools uses many states, to name a few:

- Search results state (/) - the main page of the application, contains the search bar, list of resources, pagination and display controls.

⁴⁹ UI-Router, <https://github.com/angular-ui/ui-router>

- Tool Card state (/tool/<toolID>) - the page that displays information about a tool, contains text and logic for generating graphics for the functions/inputs/outputs widget.
- Tool edit state (/tool/<toolID>/edit) - state nested under the tool card state, contains components allowing for editing a resource's annotation.
- 404 state - error 404 page, displayed when a matching state is not found for a URL.

D1.2.5 Directives

In the AngularJS world directives are a widely utilised component with very many uses. A directive is essentially a function that executes when the Angular compiler finds it in the view. A directive can be e.g. a separate component with all its logic (e.g. search bar), a reusable input field with built in error handling, a function that alters the view or behavior of a different component (e.g. control that switches between summary and grid views), or functionality that adds tabs to a view. Directives can do almost anything, and therefore it's difficult to precisely define what they are. bio.tools uses and defines many directives.

D1.2.6 Components

Here is a list of various components created within bio.tools (the list is not exhaustive):

- **Search bar** - directive that defines the search bar component. The component is based on the functionality provided by the ngTagsInput⁵⁰ library. This functionality, however, has to be extended to provide support for the resource filtering functionality. The search bar directive consists of a view that wraps a customised ngTagsInput directive, and of a controller. The controller provides necessary logic that is by default missing from the ngTagsInput library. The controller also ties in several services: one which stores query terms, one that contacts the backend for search results, one that stores terms that need to be highlighted, one that contacts the backend for search suggestions *etc.*
- **Tool list** - directive that defines the tool-list pills-view component. It consists of a view that defines the look of a pill, and of a controller. The controller ties in a service that returns search results, and a service that stores which terms should be highlighted.
- **Tool list table** - directive that defines the tool-list grid-view component. The component is based on the functionality provided by Angular UI Grid⁵¹ - a library for creating data grids. It consists of a collection of customized views, one for each column type; two controllers: one that defines the settings of the whole table and saves the table's state, and one that defines functions necessary for cells. The controllers communicate with services that store column information, return search results, and store which terms should be highlighted.
- **Tool registration** - state that defines the tool registration component. The state includes a view that defines the resource registration form, as well as the EDAM term picking widget. The attached controller is responsible for handling the form logic and controlling the EDAM term picker behavior. Amongst others, it connects to a service that retrieves the EDAM ontology from the backend.

D1.3 Compilation & Dependencies

Before every release the application is compiled using the task runner Gulp⁵². Routines have been created for Gulp that make sure that all the dependencies are present, minified and concatenated into a single file. This also happens with bio.tools code as well as all of the custom CSS. Minifying and concatenating code leads to faster page loads, since fewer requests need to be made and smaller sized files need to be

⁵⁰ ngTagsInput, <http://mbenford.github.io/ngTagsInput/>

⁵¹ Angular UI Grid, <http://ui-grid.info/>

⁵² Gulp, <http://gulpjs.com/>

downloaded. The dependencies are handled by the Node Package Manager⁵³ and Bower⁵⁴ and saved into respective configuration files.

D.2 Server-side application

D2.1 Overview

The backend is an application written in Python using Django Framework⁵⁵. The application is working against a MySQL database and offers a REST API (via Django REST Framework⁵⁶) that clients can use to access data. To facilitate fast and contextual searching, as well as rapid data retrieval, the application uses Elastic as both a search engine and a 'cache'. The application is served by the web server Apache, through the WSGI interface.

Figure 20 Server-side application architecture

D2.2 Application

The structure of the application is based on a model Django application. It consists of a number of modules that work together to receive requests, perform necessary operations (lookups, saving) and returning responses. The modules have different functions, ranging from matching URLs to views, to accessing the database. When a request from a client reaches the application, the information flows through the modules.

⁵³ NPM, <https://www.npmjs.com/>

⁵⁴ Bower, <https://bower.io/>

⁵⁵ Django Framework, <https://www.djangoproject.com/>

⁵⁶ Django REST Framework, <http://www.django-rest-framework.org/>

Figure 21 Server-side application components

D2.2.1 Models

A model is the single, definitive source of information about data⁵⁷. It contains the definitions of fields, tables and relations in the database. It also provides some low-level validation, such as enforcing field type (integer, character), maximum field length, or checking incoming data structure. In bio.tools the models describe the structure of stored resources. The models are based on biotoolsXSD. Once the models are created, the database structure can be instantiated from them.

D2.2.2 Database

bio.tools uses MySQL as its database. Since the database's structure is defined using data models, Django offers a database-abstraction API (ORM) that allows for creating, retrieving, updating and deleting objects. This allows for operating on data objects rather than writing queries manually.

D2.2.3 URLs

The URLs module maps URL paths from incoming requests to appropriate view functions. The view functions further handle the request and return a response. The URLs module defines the endpoints for the API.

D2.2.3 Parsers / Renderers

Before a request reaches the view function it passes through the parser functions. Depending on the content type of the request (JSON, XML, etc) an appropriate parsing function is ran to convert the request into native Python datatypes that view functions and serializers can use directly. View functions and serializers are content type agnostic. A similar mechanic is used for responses returned by view functions: before they are returned to the client they pass through rendering functions that convert native Python datatypes to appropriate content types. This is the step where conversion to / from an XSD schema compliant XML to native Python datatypes would happen.

bio.tools supports the following content types:

- Parsers: JSON, XML
- Renderers: JSON, XML, browsable API (HTML)

⁵⁷ Django documentation, <https://docs.djangoproject.com/en/1.8/topics/db/models/>

D2.2.4 Views

The views module contains functions that take a Web request and return a Web response. The organisation of the views is generally similar to how the API is structured. Amongst many others here are the functions for:

- retrieving a single resource
- retrieving a paginated list of all resources
- searching and retrieving a paginated list of search results
- saving a new resource
- updating an existing resource
- retrieving a list of search suggestions
- retrieving statistics of system's usage

The appropriate view functions perform all the arbitrary logic necessary to return a response. For example:

- when a request comes in to retrieve a single resource by its ID, a view function would look up the ID in the database, serialize the result using the resource serializer and return it to the client.
- when a request comes in to save a new resource, a view function would pass the resource data within the request to the resource serializer. If the deserialization passes validation it would be saved to the database.

bio.tools uses an unconventional approach to returning lists of resources. Instead of searching through the database and serializing the results, we search on and return them from an Elastic index. The rationale and a more detailed description of this process is in the section below. The view functions also employ checks for authentication and authorization, making sure that only authenticated and authorised users can save, update or delete resources.

D2.2.5 Elastic

bio.tools uses Elastic⁵⁸ as a search engine. Elastic is the most popular enterprise search engine⁵⁹. It uses a document oriented database and allows for very fast and sensible (according to our testing) searching on all of the resources stored in bio.tools, and offers a plethora of customisation options.

bio.tools also uses Elastic as a NoSQL database for returning lists of resources. When returning a list of resources (either search results, or all resources), instead of looking them up in the MySQL database and serializing each resource in a traditional manner, they are looked up and returned from Elastic. In our testing this approach was 10-15 times more performant than the conventional when returning a page with 25 resources, and even more so when returning more resources per page.

The data store of Elastic is organized into indexes, each of which has a collection of documents that can be searched on. In bio.tools the documents are serialized resources, rendered into JSON. When a new resource is to be saved in bio.tools, it is both saved in the MySQL database (for safe keeping) and added to the Elastic index (for fast search and retrieval). When existing resources are updated or deleted, this is reflected both in the MySQL database and the index.

Elastic is ran as a standalone application alongside the bio.tools application. Elastic exposes an API that bio.tools uses via the official Elasticsearch Python client. When a request is made to bio.tools asking to perform a search on content, the appropriate view function calls a method that creates an Elastic-style query

⁵⁸ Elastic, <https://www.elastic.co/>

⁵⁹ Search engine ranking, <http://db-engines.com/en/ranking/search+engine>

object, which is then sent to the Elastic index via the API. The result of the search returned from the API is then rendered in the suitable content type, and returned in a response.

bio.tools has methods for recreating an entire Elastic index from the contents of the MySQL database.

D2.2.6 Serializers

Serializers provide a mechanism for converting complex data such as database objects - Django querysets and models - into native Python datatypes that can then be easily rendered into JSON, XML or other content types. Serializers also provide deserialization, allowing parsed data to be converted back into complex types, to be later saved into the database⁶⁰. Serializers allow for high-level validation to be performed, such as making sure that EDAM terms are valid. Serializers are used to make sure that the incoming data (such as a resource) is correct.

Each object from the XSD schema (such as resource, function, contact), has a serializer created for it. The serializers can be nested, giving support for nested objects, such as, *e.g.* a resource, that has multiple functions, that each have multiple inputs, *etc.* What fields will be serialized can be chosen, so even if the database holds some meta information (internal id, datetime when object created), these can be left unserialized, and therefore will not be returned to the client.

D2.2.7 Admin panel

The admin panel is created using the admin site functionality built into Django. It is mostly created automatically based on the model definitions, with some configuration needed. It allows trusted users (admins, curators) to manage content on bio.tools. The admin site allows to enter content that normally would not pass validation, and therefore is intended to be used only by trusted users, who are aware of the implications. The admin panel allows to alter all database contents of bio.tools, such as registered resources, user accounts etc.

D2.2.8 Authentication and Authorization, Security

bio.tools uses the authentication and authorization frameworks build into Django, with some additions. Instead of using default cookie-based user sessions, token based authentication provided by Django REST framework is used. After a client logs in, they receive a token, that has to be added to the header of every subsequent request. By having the token in the header of requests the application can recognise different users. The token expires after 7 days.

Additionally, Django REST Auth⁶¹ is used to provide an API for user login, account retrieval, resetting and changing passwords. Django AllAuth⁶² is used to provide an API for registering new accounts. When a new account is registered a validation email is sent to the registering user.

Authorization is handled by permission classes from Django REST Framework. The built-in classes allow for ensuring that new objects can be created by logged in users, while existing objects can only be manipulated by their logged in owners. The permissions system in Django REST is future-proof by being very extensible and allowing for freedom of customisation.

The application is served over HTTPS, with a modern, up-to-date SSL certificate, therefore the end-to-end communication between a client and the server is encrypted. User passwords are managed using Django's

⁶⁰ Django REST Framework documentation, <http://www.django-rest-framework.org/api-guide/serializers/>

⁶¹ Django REST Auth, <http://django-rest-auth.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

⁶² Django AllAuth, <http://www.intenct.nl/projects/django-allauth/>

default mechanisms⁶³. The secret key, used for cryptographic signing of transient data (such as links in confirmation emails, or password reset links), is stored on the server, and not added to the code repository.

D2.2.9 Unit tests

Over 750 unit tests have been written that ensure the application is robust and less error prone. bio.tools uses the testing framework build into Django to create and run the tests. The tests are run after every change to the backend code.

D3 Server

The server-side application is served by the web server Apache, through the WSGI interface. The client-side application is served by the same Apache as static files. The server also runs a MySQL database and an Elastic server application.

Figure 22 Server architecture

D3.1 Hardware

bio.tools is running on a virtual machine provided by DTU. The hardware machine has Intel Xeon(R) CPU E5-2683 v3 processors, of which 20 cores belong to bio.tools. The RAM available is variable, at a minimum of 4GB. The operating system installed is Ubuntu 14.04 LTS.

D3.2 Deployment

The application can be deployed on local and remote servers using Vagrant⁶⁴ and Ansible⁶⁵. For remote installations an Ansible provisioning scheme has been created.

The provisioner:

- installs all the necessary packages
- installs Apache, MySQL and Elastic
- creates / sets permissions for directories that bio.tools code will be put in
- downloads the newest version of bio.tools code from the repository

⁶³ Django password management, <https://docs.djangoproject.com/en/1.8/topics/auth/passwords/>

⁶⁴ Vagrant, <https://www.vagrantup.com/>

⁶⁵ Ansible, <https://www.ansible.com/>

- configures Apache to serve both the client and server bio.tools applications
- sets up SSL keys and certificates in Apache
- configures MySQL with an empty database (if one does not exist already) and creates users with permissions to access it

For local, development installations a Vagrantfile has been created. The Vagrantfile has a definition of a virtual machine that it will create, along with users and port forwarding, and a command to run the Ansible provisioner automatically, once the virtual machine is ready.